

Georeferenced mapping of POIs regarding accessibility and standardised adaptation plans (PEPA) in case of barriers

Deliverable 4.1

Version 2.0

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List of abbreviations (English)

API	Application programming interface
App	Application
Cm	Centimeter
CMS	Content management system
CSV	Comma-separated values
D	Deliverable
DE	Germany
E.g.	For example
GPS	Global positioning system
HTML	HyperText Mark-up Language
I.e.	That is
IG-VAE	Guaranteed Information for Accessibility Evaluation Based on Individual Needs
IND	independent L. ONLUS
IT	Italy
LP	Lead Partner
M	Meter
MIND Centre	Meran.o Innovation District
PEBA	Plan for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers (formerly <i>PEPA</i>)
POI	Point of Interest
QR Code	Quick-response code
SEV	Rail replacement service
T	Task
URL	Uniform resource locator

List of abbreviations (German)

BBM	Baubeginnmeldung
BP.-Nr.	Bauparzelle
DLH	Dekrete des Landeshauptmanns
KG	Katastralgemeinde
z.B.	Zum Beispiel

List of abbreviations (Italian)

ad es.	Ad esempio
C.C.	Comune Catastale
D.I.A.	Denuncia inizio attività
D.P.P.	Decreto del Presidente della Provincia
P. ed.	Particella Edilizia

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Administrative information

Basic information on the SuCoLo project and this deliverable:

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Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to systematically assess, document, and propose targeted interventions for improving accessibility at the SuCoLo project's pilot sites in Merano, Italy and Leipzig, Germany. As part of T4.1 *Design and prepare accessible and inclusive pilots with local stakeholders* and T4.2 *Run and evaluate pilots in communities of local neighbourhoods*, this manuscript shines a light on the accessibility and inclusiveness attributes of SuCoLo's pilot sites in Leipzig (DE) and Merano (IT). It serves as both a technical and operational reference for identifying architectural, sensory, and informational barriers that may hinder equal access to infrastructure and services, particularly in the context of sustainable bicycle logistics. Through the application of georeferenced POI mapping and the development of Standardised Adaptation Plans (PEBA), the document provides an evidence-based framework for prioritising investments, estimating adaptation costs, and aligning proposed measures with applicable accessibility regulations and best practices.

This deliverable is intended to guide project partners, municipal authorities, and other stakeholders in making informed, data-driven decisions to enhance inclusivity and mobility in urban outskirts. By integrating spatial analysis, on-site surveys, and multi-criteria accessibility evaluations, it ensures that recommendations are not only compliant with legislative standards but also responsive to the practical needs of *all* user groups, including persons with disabilities, older adults, and families. The document thus plays a role in translating the SuCoLo project's vision of sustainable, inclusive urban logistics into actionable, measurable outcomes.

This document is complemented with D4.2 *Innovative 3D tours describing the accessibility and inclusion of pilot sites according to the IG-VAE methodology*, which were designed to digitally visualise the accessibility and inclusivity of SuCoLo's two pilot sites and their surrounding points of interest (POIs) using the IG-VAE methodology (Guaranteed Information for Accessibility Evaluation Based on Individual Needs).

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the georeferenced mapping of Points of Interest (POIs), and the elaboration of standardised adaptation plans for the elimination of architectural barriers (known as *PEBA*) at two SuCoLo pilot sites and their surrounding area: the Merano Innovation District (MIND Centre) in Merano, Italy, and the Lützschena tram stop near Leipzig, Germany. Locations that have functional, social, or economic relevance to users of that site (i.e., POIs) were located and assessed, with specific courses of action if they were to become fully accessible - thereby enabling *all* citizens to engage in sustainable delivery innovations (i.e., via Leipzig's delivery micro-hub and Merano's parcel pick-up station). In doing so, this deliverable directly supports SuCoLo WP4's goal to digitally showcase surrounding POIs and their accessibility and inclusivity attributes, audit the extent of actual versus desired accessibility in selected sites, and in doing so, support the conception and development of the SuCoLo pilot sites aimed to cater to *all* user groups.

For both locations, extensive on-site accessibility assessments were conducted, mapping 402 POIs (366 in Merano and 36 in Leipzig) and developed / published an open-access online plug-in that displays both map and list views in local languages. Each POI was classified (e.g., as a participant business, parking space, etc.) and evaluated according to accessibility attributes such as compliance level, barriers, and available services in an interactive map. For the POIs most pertinent to the SuCoLo pilots, targeted PEBA adaptation plans were developed that address architectural, sensory, and informational accessibility gaps.

At the Merano pilot site, the MIND Centre was rated with good overall accessibility ('C'), but with significant gaps for people with sensory impairments and a lack of nearby reserved parking. Improvement measures - estimated at over €90.000 - include improvements such as creating accessible parking and charging stations, upgrading signage, installing tactile guidance systems, enhancing sanitary facilities, improving ramps and entrances, and integrating induction hearing loops. Similar evaluations were performed for surrounding infrastructure such as the Maia Bassa railway station and nearby bus stops, with proposals for tactile paths, shelter improvements, and compliant seating.

In Leipzig, the Lützschena tram stop was found to be non-compliant, lacking raised platforms, safe boarding areas, and weather protection. Recommended upgrades (around €215.000) include complete reconstruction into a barrier-free stop with raised kerbs, accessible shelters, tactile guidance systems, compliant seating, designated parking, and the installation of an accessible family toilet nearby. These changes aim to support safe, inclusive, and sustainable mobility in a peripheral district that connects to key freight and public transport networks.

Overall, the georeferenced POI mapping and PEBA adaptation plans form a replicable methodology for identifying, documenting, and addressing accessibility barriers in urban outskirts. As well, the files that compose the POI plug-in tool are openly accessible and adaptable to different contexts, and a developer's guide (located in the appendix) that describes the files that hold the POI plug-in tool in greater detail.

The points of interest surrounding the SuCoLo pilot sites can be accessed here:

Merano research pilot: <https://sucolo.independent.it/>

Leipzig research pilot: <https://sucolo.independent.it/lipsia/>

Complementing the developers' guide to adapt and implement the plug-in tool located in the appendix, the plug-in tool itself and the files therein, as well as the developers' guide in Italian and German can be accessed here:

SuCoLo open access repository:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/sucolo/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

1. Georeferenced Mapping of Points of Interest

For the two research pilots in Merano and Leipzig, geospatially referenced locations that have functional, social, or economic relevance to users of that site - referred to as Points of Interest (POIs) - were listed, categorised and mapped via an online plug-in on a website. The POIs collected relate to the catchment area of the two SuCoLo pilot sites in Merano (Maia Bassa) and Leipzig (Lützschena-Stahmeln). As such, they had not to fulfil certain hard criteria. As 'useful information' for people with disabilities, senior citizens and families with small children and prams, a focus was employed primarily on mobility in the 15-minute city (mobility centres, bus stops, reserved parking spaces, charging stations, accessible toilets, etc.) and the presence of information points for families when selecting the relevant points. The inventory shows the corresponding services and assesses their general accessibility. As in the entire SuCoLo pilot site in Leipzig (Lützschena-Stahmeln) did not possess any reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities, it was decided to include other points of interest in the area and display them in a user-friendly way to improve inner-city mobility.

The plug-in on the website allows one to view the POIs in both a list view and a map view, and it is available in the native languages of the pilot sites: German and Italian. This website is fully open access, and credentials are not needed.

Each POI was categorised into classifications, such as:

- Participant business
- Parking space
- Charging station
- Accessible toilet facilities
- Public transportation
- Info point

Furthermore, each POI was described according to the following (accessibility) attributes:

- Extent of accessibility for people with a disability (on a scale from 1-5)
- Basic description
- Accessibility characteristics
- Accessibility obstacles
- Accessibility orientation
- Notes
- Contact information
- Services
- Accessibility features

In total, 402 POIs were denoted, with 36 in Leipzig (Lützschena and surrounding area) and 366 in Merano. To learn more about how this plug-in is structured and how developers can customize it by adapting it to the various Content Management Systems (CMSs) currently in use, please refer to Appendix 1 *Developers' guide: Structure of the georeferenced POIs plug-in and adapting it to various content management systems*.

Figure 1 Screenshot of the interactive website mapping the points of interest in Merano (source: <https://sucolo.independent.it/de/>)

Figure 2 Screenshot of the interactive website mapping the points of interest in Leipzig (source: <https://sucolo.independent.it/lipsia/>)

Figure 3 Screenshots of POI descriptions (source: <https://sucolo.independent.it/de/>)

2. Standardised adaptation plans in case of barriers (PEBA)

An on-site survey was taken around the SuCoLo research pilots' infrastructure and surrounding area to assess its degree of accessibility and suggest actionable renovation suggestions if the sites were to be renovated to be fully accessible to all user groups. These take the form of standardised adaptation plans, specifically Plans for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers (known as *PEBA*).

The on-site survey aims to describe barrier-free accessibility for people with disabilities. In order to cover as wide a range of special needs as possible and, in particular, to take into account the needs of families with prams and senior citizens, it was decided to work according to the internationally recognised IG-VAE method¹. This method involves checking structures on site and collecting as many factual, objective parameters and attributes as possible to describe barrier-free accessibility. A factual accessibility description is then created, with photos and supplementary data where possible. The aim of the method is to enable everyone to decide for themselves, based on the objective information provided, whether an existing offer meets their personal/individual requirements or is suitable for them. This principle has proven itself for years, for example in the tourism portal 'Alto Adige per tutti'² and is recognised as best practice at European level.

The specific technical survey form that was used for the SuCoLo project was based on the official technical standard survey form of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano – South Tyrol (Office for Construction Contracts – Building Construction and Technical Services Department³) for categorising the barrier-free accessibility of public buildings and facilities. Following this standard, the accessibility category **A**, **B** or **C** of a building is assigned according to the following criteria:

A: The majority priority issues do NOT comply with legal requirements, regardless of whether the secondary positions are compliant or not.

B: SOME of the priority and secondary issues are NOT in accordance with regulations.

C: ALL priority issues are compliant, and only a few secondary positions do not comply with the directive.

While conducting the on-site survey, the following priority and secondary issues were considered:

Priority issues

- There is no route to access the building that can be used independently by all users
- The access door does not have the minimum width of 90 cm
- The internal routes do not provide adequate manoeuvring space

¹ <https://www.altoadigepertutti.it/de/tourismusvereine>

² <https://www.altoadigepertutti.it/de/home>

³ <https://costruire.provincia.bz.it/it/home>

- There is no lift
- There are no accessible toilets
- The door threshold and the rooms in front of and behind it are not coplanar

Secondary issues

- The ramps do not comply with the standard values specified in the standard
- There are no regulation car parking spaces near the entrance
- There are no clear spaces measuring 1.50 x 1.50 m in front of and behind the entrance
- The stairs are not marked with appropriate floor markings
- The handrail is not $0.95 < h < 1.05$ m high and/or the railing is not $h = 1.00$ m high
- The existing lift does not comply with regulations
- There is no stair lift
- The toilets/showers do not comply with the latest regulations
- There is no changing room (only in facilities where one is provided)
- The windows do not meet the specified requirements (without adaptation costs)
- The electrical devices are not easy to use (without adaptation costs)
- There is no bell or door intercom system at the entrance that complies with regulations
- There is no information point and no call bell
- There is no vertical signage and no floor markings

Thereafter, the following feedback was handed over to the respective operating company to consider for prospective improvements.

2.1. Standardised adaptation plans in Merano

This section denotes the background and contextual factors concerning the research pilot site in Merano and its surrounding area, the on-site surveys taken, along with detailed recommendations for improvement to be fully accessible to *all* user groups (including user groups with physical, sensory, intellectual, cognitive disabilities).

2.1.1. Background

In Merano, the Merano Innovation District (MIND Centre) is an initiative of the Municipality of Merano to strengthen the spirit of innovation, creativity and entrepreneurial culture in the Merano region. It promotes and supports start-ups and established companies, educators and interested citizens, with the aim of creating economic and social development in the area. As part of the SuCoLo project, the MIND Centre was chosen as the strategic location for the cargo bike-specific pickup station because it is:

- Located in the less connected outskirts of Merano
- In proximity to Maia Bassa railway station (350 m)
- Directly connected to the main bicycle network
- Connected to the public transport net (bus lines)
- Barrier-free accessible and encourages general accessibility for all
- A public building of the municipality of Merano (project partner)
- A Point of cooperation between public administration and the local economy
- Supported by the Merano Galoppo, the owner of the entire area around the MIND Centre, and backs the SuCoLo project

The access to the MIND Centre is in Via delle Palade Street 86. There is no designated parking space, but customers with a disabled parking permit can park their car in front of the entrance. The entrance to the MIND Centre is located underneath the steps of tribune B (house number 92A). The MIND Centre is accessible and has two accessible toilets (south toilets and north toilets). All rooms are accessible without steps via an internal ramp. In the entrance area, there are a few inaccessible places to sit, where the pavement is made of gravel. The kitchen is equipped with high tables. There are no tactile orientation aids for the visually impaired. The nearby Ippodromo bar is located at the main entrance of the racecourse and is not accessible. However, only the tables on the terrace on the forecourt are accessible without steps.

Figure 4 Map of Merano with districts (with Merano Maia Bassa & MIND Centre framed in green) (source: <https://www.openstreetmap.org>)

Figure 5 Map section of the Merano pilot district Maia Bassa with transport connections (source: <https://www.openstreetmap.org>)

2.1.2. On-site survey

Table 1 On-site survey conducted at the MIND Centre

Bewohnbarkeitsbescheinig. (gemäß G. vom 09 Januar 1989, Nr.13) Certificato di abitabilità (conformità alla L. 09 gennaio 1989, n°13) Certificate of habitability (compliance with Law no. 13 of January 9 th 1989)	Ja/Si/Yes	Nein/No/No	Datum/Data/Date
Ansuchen um Ausnahmegenehmigung laut Art. 8 Richiesta di deroga come Art. 8 Request for Exemption according to Art. 8	Ja/Si/Yes		Nein/No/No
Gebäudeinstandhaltungskode: Codice manutenzione edificio: Building maintenance code:			
Adresse: Indirizzo: Address:	Gampenstraße 92 A / via delle Pallade 92 A / via delle Pallade street 92 A		
BP.-Nr.: P. ed.: Building parcel no.:			
KG: C.C.: Cadastral municipality:			
Nutzungsart: Destinazione d'uso: Utilisation of the building:	Büroflächen und Coworking Space / Uffici e spazi di coworking / Offices and coworking space		
Baujahr und Datum Umbau: Anno di costruzione e data di ristrutturazione: Year of construction and date of renovation:	Pferderennplatz 1935 – Umbau und Eröffnung MIND 2023 Ippodromo 1935 - Ricostruzione e apertura MIND 2023 Racecourse 1935 - Renovation and opening MIND 2023		
Bestandsaufnahme bzgl. DLH 54 - 9 November 2009 Stato attuale in rif. D.P.P. 54 - 9 novembre 2009	A	B	C
Geschätzte Kosten Costo stimato Estimated adaptation costs	Baukosten / Costo lavori / Adaptation costs in €: 67.000,00 Zur Verfügung stehende Beträge 35% in €: 23.450,00 Somme a disposizione 35% in €: Available sums 35% in €: GESAMTKOSTEN / TOTALE / TOTAL COSTS IN €: 90.450,00		
Für die Anpassung des Gebäudes laut DLH vom 09 November 2009 ist folgendes erforderlich Per l'adeguamento del fabbricato ai sensi del D.P.P. 09 novembre 2009 è necessario The following is required for the adaptation of the building according to the Decree of the President of the Province of Bolzano dated November 09 th 2009	Projekt <i>Progetto</i>	Baukonzession <i>Concessione Edilizia</i>	BBM <i>D.I.A.</i>
Der Techniker / Il Tecnico / The Technician	Erhebungsdatum / Data del rilevamento / Survey date: 15/10/2024 Magister Günther Ennemoser (IND) Geom. Giorgio Pantano (IND)		

Artikel Articolo Article	Beschreibung Descrizione Description	Ja Si Yes	Nein No No	Kosten € Costo € Costs €	Anmerkungen Osservazioni Notes
Reservierte Parkplätze für Menschen mit Behinderungen Parcheggi riservati per persone con disabilità Reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities					
22	Reservierte Parkplätze sind in erforderlicher Anzahl in der Nähe des Eingangs vorhanden? --- Sono presenti posti auto riservati per persone con disabilità in numero adeguato vicino all'ingresso? --- Are there an adequate number of reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities near the entrance?		X	1.500,00	In unmittelbarer Nähe zum Eingang gibt es keine reservierten Parkplätze für Menschen mit Behinderungen (nicht ausgewiesen oder entsprechend gekennzeichnet). --- Non ci sono parcheggi riservati alle persone con disabilità nelle immediate vicinanze dell'ingresso (non designati o segnalati). --- There are no reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities in the immediate vicinity of the entrance (not designated or signed).
	Fällt in die Zuständigkeit des Landes, der Gemeinde oder gilt etwas Anderes? --- Ricade nella competenza della provincia, del comune o altro? --- Does it fall under the competence of the province, the municipality or someone else?				Fällt in die Zuständigkeit der Gemeinde. --- Ricade nella competenza del comune. --- It falls within the competence of the municipality.
24	Befindet sich die Haltestelle des öffentlichen Verkehrsmittels in unmittelbarer Nähe des Gebäudeeingangs? --- La fermata dei mezzi pubblici è nelle immediate vicinanze dell'ingresso dell'edificio? --- Is the public transport stop in the immediate vicinity of the building entrance?		X	8.500,00	Normgerechte Adaptierung Bushaltestellen. --- Messa a norma delle fermate degli autobus. --- Making bus stops compliant.
53	Ist die vertikale und horizontale Beschilderung vorhanden? --- È presente la segnaletica verticale ed orizzontale? --- Is there vertical and horizontal signage?	X			
Zugang zum Gebäude Accesso all'edificio Access to the building					
33	Der Zugang zum Gebäude ist selbstständig benutzbar? ---	X			Für Coworker offen von 6.00-24.00 Uhr, Kernzeiten Parteienverkehr von 10.00-13.00 Uhr.

	<p>Il percorso fino all'edificio è accessibile autonomamente? --- Is the access path to the building independently accessible?</p>				<p>--- Aperto per i collaboratori/coworker dalle 6.00 alle 24.00, orario al pubblico dalle 10.00 alle 13.00. --- Open for coworkers 6.00-24.00, core hours party traffic 10.00-13.00.</p>
20	<p>Die vorhandenen Rampen sind normgemäß? --- Le rampe di accesso sono a norma? --- Are the access ramps compliant?</p>		X	1.600,00	<p>- Die interne Rampe vom Empfangsbereich zum Coworking Space (2 Abschnitte) hat keinen Handlauf und sollte auf beiden Seiten mit einem normgerechten Handlauf ausgestattet werden; --- - La rampa interna che porta dalla reception allo spazio di coworking (2 tratti) è priva di corrimano e dovrebbe esserne dotata di uno a norma su entrambi i lati; --- - The internal ramp from the reception area to the coworking space (2 sections) has no handrail and should be fitted with a compliant handrail on both sides;</p>
34.2 + 48.1b	<p>Die lichte Breite der Eingangstür ist > 90 cm? --- La porta d'accesso ha una luce netta > 90 cm? --- The clear width of the entrance door is > 90 cm?</p>		X	7.500,00	<p>- Zugangsschwierigkeiten aufgrund der zweiflügeligen Eingangstür (70+70 cm): Vorschlag Austausch Eingangstür durch eine automatische Schiebetür; --- - Difficoltà di accesso a causa della porta d'ingresso a due ante (70+70 cm): si propone la sostituzione con una porta scorrevole automatica; --- - Access difficulties due to the double-leaf entrance door (70+70 cm): Proposal to replace the entrance door with an automatic sliding door;</p>
34.6	<p>Die Rotationsfläche vor und hinter dem Eingang ist > 1,50 m x 1,50 m? --- Lo spazio di rotazione antistante e retrostante l'accesso è > 1,50 m x 1,50 m? --- Is the maneuvering space in front of and behind the access > 1.50 m x 1.50 m?</p>	X			
34.6	<p>Der Eingangsbereich ist witterungsgeschützt, es gibt eine Überdachung? --- La zona d'ingresso è protetta dagli agenti atmosferici, è presente una tettoia? --- Is the entrance area protected from the weather, is there a roof?</p>	X			
51.1a	<p>Sind die normgemäße Türglocke und Gegensprechanlage vorhanden (90-120 cm)? --- All'accesso sono presenti campanello e citofono a norma (90-120 cm)?</p>		X	700,00	<p>- Ausstattung des Eingangs mit Hausnummer 92A mit einer Türklingel mit Gegensprechanlage; ---</p>

	<p>--- Is there a compliant bell and intercom at the entrance (90-120 cm)?</p>				<p>- Dotazione dell'ingresso del numero civico 92A con un campanello con citofono; --- - Equipping the entrance with house number 92A with a doorbell with intercom;</p>
<p>Interne Verbindungswege Percorsi interni Internal connection paths</p>					
35.3	<p>Die Gangbreite ist > 1,50 m? --- Il corridoio ha una larghezza > 1,50 m? --- Does the corridor have a width > 1,50 m?</p>	X			
48	<p>Die lichte Breite der Innentüren ist > 80 cm? --- Le porte interne hanno una luce netta > 80 cm? --- The clear width of the interior doors is > 80 cm?</p>	X			<p>- Einzig die Tür zur Toilette des WCs Süd weist aufgrund des Antipanikgriffs nur eine Durchgangsbreite von 77 cm auf; --- - Solo la porta della toilette nel WC sud ha una larghezza di passaggio inferiore (77 cm) a causa del maniglione antipanico; --- - Only the door to the toilet in the south WC has a passage width of just 77 cm due to the anti-panic handle;</p>
48.1a	<p>Die Türschwellen und die davor und dahinter befindlichen Bereiche sind niveaugleich, bzw. die Schwelle ist < 2,5 cm? --- Le soglie delle porte e gli spazi antistanti e retrostanti sono complanari o la soglia è < 2,5 cm? --- Are the door thresholds and spaces in front and behind coplanar or is the threshold < 2,5 cm?</p>	X			
47.3 + 53.3	<p>Vom Eingang bis zum Auskunftsschalter/Aufzug gibt es eine taktile Bodenmarkierung? --- Dall'ingresso all'infopoint/ascensore è presente la segnaletica a pavimento tattile? --- Is there tactile floor signage from the entrance to the infopoint/lift?</p>		X	27.000,0	<p>- Realisierung eines taktilen Leitweges und eines taktilen Übersichtsplans im Außenbereich bis zum Infopoint (Rezeption); --- - Realizzazione di un percorso guida e di una mappa tattili nell'area esterna fino all'Infopoint (reception); --- - Realisation of a tactile guide path and a tactile map in the outdoor area all the way to the InfoPoint (reception);</p>
<p>Sanitäranlagen Servizi igienici Sanitary facilities</p>					
44	<p>Sind normgemäße sanitäre Anlagen vorhanden? --- Esistono servizi igienici a norma? ---</p>	X			

	Are there compliant barrier-free toilets?				
44	<p>Sind die sanitären Einrichtungen und das Zubehör normgemäß? ---</p> <p>Gli apparecchi sanitari e gli accessori sono a norma? ---</p> <p>Do sanitary appliances and accessories comply with standards?</p>		X	1.200,00	<p>WC NORD: - Kennzeichnung barrierefreies WC fehlt; - Verlängerung Zugschnur der Alarmklingel bis fast auf den Boden; - Schaffung zugänglicher Ablageflächen und Aufhängehaken im barrierefreien WC; - Herabsetzung eines Pissaires auf eine kindgerechte Höhe von 50 cm (Schnabelhöhe); - Schaffung eines barrierefreien Wickeltisches im Unisex-Bereich;</p> <p>WC SÜD: - Kennzeichnung barrierefreies WC fehlt; - Verlängerung Zugschnur der Alarmklingel bis fast auf den Boden; - Schaffung zugänglicher Ablageflächen und Aufhängehaken im barrierefreien WC; - Schaffung eines barrierefreien Wickeltisches im Unisex-Bereich; ---</p> <p>WC NORD: - Manca la segnalazione del bagno accessibile; - Prolungamento del cavo di trazione del campanello d'allarme quasi fino al pavimento; - Creazione di mensole e ganci accessibili nel WC accessibile; - Abbassamento di un orinatoio a un'altezza adatta ai bambini di 50 cm (altezza del becco); - Creazione di un fasciatoio accessibile nell'area unisex;</p> <p>WC SUD: - Manca la segnalazione del bagno accessibile; - Prolungamento del cavo di trazione del campanello d'allarme quasi fino al pavimento; - Creazione di mensole e ganci accessibili nel WC accessibile; - Creazione di un fasciatoio accessibile nell'area unisex; ---</p> <p>WC NORD: - Labelling of barrier-free WC missing; - Extension of the alarm bell pull cord almost to the floor; - Creation of accessible shelves and hanging hooks in the accessible toilet; - Lowering a urinal to a child-friendly height of 50 cm (beak height); - Creation of a barrier-free changing table in the unisex area;</p> <p>WC SOUTH: - Labelling of barrier-free WC missing;</p>

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extension of the alarm bell pull cord almost to the floor; - Creation of accessible shelves and hanging hooks in the accessible toilet; - Creation of an accessible changing table in the unisex area;
45	<p>Sind normgemäÙe Duschen vorhanden? ---</p> <p>Esistono docce a norma? ---</p> <p>Are there showers that comply with standards?</p>	/			
46	<p>Gibt es einen zugänglichen Umkleideraum? (nur bei Gebäuden, wo ein solcher vorgesehen ist) ---</p> <p>Esiste lo spogliatoio accessibile? (solo per le strutture che lo prevedono) ---</p> <p>Is there an accessible changing room? (only for facilities that provide it)</p>	/			
44 + 45 +46	<p>Im Falle von mehreren Sanitäranlagen: In jeder vorhandenen Sanitärgruppe ist jeweils eine Sanitäranlage laut Art. 44, 45 und 46 vorhanden? ---</p> <p>In caso di più servizi igienici: In ogni gruppo di servizi igienici presente c'è un servizio ai sensi dell'art. 44, 45 e 46? ---</p> <p>In the case of several sanitary facilities: Is there in each group of sanitary facilities present a toilet within the meaning of Art. 44, 45 and 46?</p>	X			
<p>Aufzugsanlagen Impianti di sollevamento Escalator</p>					
39	<p>Gibt es einen Aufzug? ---</p> <p>Esiste un ascensore? ---</p> <p>Is there a lift?</p>		/		
39	<p>Entspricht der bestehende Aufzug den geltenden Vorschriften laut Art. 39 (im Schulneubau laut Art. 55 - AufzugmaÙe, Türen, Bedientafel, Alarm usw.)? ---</p> <p>L'ascensore è a norma ai sensi dell'art. 39 (nell'edilizia scolastica ai sensi dell'art. 55 - dimensioni, porte, pulsantiera, allarme ecc.)? ---</p> <p>Is the lift compliant according to Art. 39 (in school buildings according to Art. 55 - dimensions, doors, push button panel, alarm, etc.)?</p>		/		

40	<p>Ist es notwendig, einen Treppenaufzug zu installieren? --- È necessario installare un servoscala? --- Is it necessary to install a stair lift?</p>		/		
<p>Treppen Scale Stairs</p>					
36 - 37	<p>Sind die Treppen, Stufen, Brüstungen, Handläufe normgemäß? --- Scale, gradini, parapetti, corrimano sono a norma? --- Are stairs, steps, parapets, handrails in compliance?</p>		X	1.100,00	<p>- Die Treppe hat keinen Handlauf: Die Stufen müssten beidseitig mit einem Handlauf gemäß UNI-Norm 10809 ausgestattet werden (Montagehöhe 95-105 cm); - Kennzeichnung aller 3 Auftritte durch kontrastierende Material- und Farbkombinationen auf einer von der Trittstufenkante aus gemessener Tiefe von 5 cm und auf der gesamten Stufenbreite; - Anbringung einer taktilen Bodenmarkierung mindestens 30 cm vor der An- und Austrittsstufe; --- - La scala è priva di corrimano: le rampe di scale devono essere dotate di un corrimano su entrambi i lati secondo la norma UNI 10809 (altezza di montaggio 95-105 cm); - Segnalazione di tutte e 3 le pedate con combinazioni di materiali e colori contrastanti ad una profondità di 5 cm misurata dal bordo della pedata e per tutta la larghezza della stessa; - Installazione di segnaletica tattile sul pavimento ad almeno 30 cm davanti ai gradini di ingresso e di uscita; -- - The steps have no handrail: The steps would have to be fitted with a handrail on both sides in accordance with UNI standard 10809 (installation height 95-105 cm); - Marking of all 3 treads with contrasting material and colour combinations at a depth of 5 cm measured from the edge of the tread and across the entire width of the tread; - Installation of tactile floor markings at least 30 cm in front of the entrance and exit steps;</p>
37.1	<p>Es gibt einen beidseitigen Handlauf entlang der Treppen? --- Su entrambi i lati delle scale è presente un corrimano? --- Is there a handrail on both sides of the stairs?</p>		X		
37.2	<p>Ist die Höhe des Handlaufs $0,95 < h < 1,05$ m und die der Brüstung $h = 1,00$ m? ---</p>		/		

	<p>Il corrimano ha altezza $0,95 < h < 1,05$ m e il parapetto $h = 1,00$ m? --- Does the handrail have height $0.95 < h < 1.05$ m and the parapet $h = 1.00$ m?</p>				
<p>Komplementäre Arbeiten Opere complementari Complementary works</p>					
49	<p>Entsprechen die Fenster den vorgesehenen Erfordernissen? (ohne Anpassungskosten) --- Le finestre rispondono ai requisiti previsti? (senza costo per l'adattamento) --- Do the windows comply with the requirements? (no cost for adaptation)</p>	X		600,00	<p>- Schließfächer: Vorschlag Kennzeichnung der tiefer gelegenen Fächer für Menschen mit Behinderungen; - Küche: Anschaffung eines barrierefreien Tisches zum Zubereiten und Essen; --- - Armadietti: si suggerisce di etichettare gli armadietti inferiori per le persone con disabilità; - Cucina: acquisto di un tavolo accessibile per preparare e consumare i pasti; --- - Lockers: Suggestion for labelling the lower lockers for people with disabilities; - Kitchen: Purchase of an accessible table for preparing and eating;</p>
50	<p>Weist die Schwelle einen Höhenunterschied von mehr als 2,5 cm auf? --- La soglia presenta un dislivello superiore a 2,5 cm? --- Does the threshold have a difference in height of more than 2.5 cm?</p>		X	450,00	<p>- Die Sitzgelegenheiten im Rezeptionsbereich sind für Menschen mit Gehbehinderungen und Sehbehinderungen aufgrund der Bodengestaltung nur bedingt zugänglich und sollten entsprechend barrierefrei adaptiert werden (z.B. höhengleicher Natursteinfliesenboden); --- - I posti a sedere nell'area della reception hanno un'accessibilità condizionata per le persone con disabilità motorie e visive a causa del design del pavimento e dovrebbero essere adattati in modo da essere privi di barriere (ad esempio, pavimento piastrellato in pietra naturale a livello); --- - Nevertheless, the seating in the reception area has conditional accessibility for persons with mobility and visual impairments due to the design of the floor and should be adapted to be barrier-free (e.g. natural stone tiled floor at the same height);</p>
51	<p>Sind die elektrischen Vorrichtungen leicht zu gebrauchen? (ohne Anpassungskosten) --- I dispositivi elettrici sono facilmente utilizzabili? (senza costo per l'adattamento) --- Are electrical devices easy to use? (no cost for adaptation)</p>		X	3.500,00	<p>- Die Meetingräume sollten mit einer induktiven Höranlage für Menschen mit Hörbehinderungen ausgestattet werden; --- - Le sale riunioni potrebbero essere dotate di un impianto ad induzione magnetica per le persone con problemi di udito; --- - The meeting rooms should be equipped with an inductive hearing</p>

					system for people with hearing impairments;
Beschilderung Segnaletica Signage					
53	<p>Es gibt eine Rufglocke mit Gegensprechanlage und/oder einen Infopoint? --- Esiste campanello con citofono e/o un Infopoint? --- Is there a bell with intercom and/or an Infopoint?</p>		X	1.600,00	<p>- Ausstattung des Eingangs mit Hausnummer 92A mit einer Türklingel mit Gegensprechanlage (unter 51.1a veranschlagt); - Rezeptionstischhöhe 120 cm und nicht unterfahrbar: Vorschlag zum Aufstellen eines barrierefreien unterfahrbaren Beistelltisches (Tischplattenhöhe 70-75, Freiraum darunter >68 cm, mit 4 Tischbeinen an den Ecken, 2 Stühle und 2 nicht bestuhlte Seiten); - Die Rezeption sollte mit einer induktiven Höranlage für Menschen mit Hörbehinderungen ausgestattet werden; --- - Dotare l'ingresso del numero civico 92A di un campanello con citofono (stimato al punto 51.1a); - Scrivania della reception alta 120 cm e non accessibile alle sedie a rotelle: proposta di allestimento di un tavolo laterale accessibile alle sedie a rotelle (altezza del piano del tavolo 70-75, spazio libero sottostante >68 cm, con 4 gambe del tavolo agli angoli, 2 sedie e 2 lati senza sedie); - La reception dovrebbe essere dotata di un sistema acustico ad induzione magnetica per le persone con disabilità di udito; --- - Equipping the entrance with house number 92A with a doorbell with intercom (estimated under 51.1a); - Reception desk height 120 cm and not wheelchair-accessible: proposal to set up a wheelchair-accessible side table (table top height 70-75, free space underneath >68 cm, with 4 table legs at the corners, 2 chairs and 2 sides without chairs); - The reception should be equipped with an inductive hearing system for people with hearing impairments;</p>
53	<p>Die Beschilderung zur Orientierung und Benützung der baulichen Einrichtungen ist ausreichend? Der empfohlene Zugangsweg für Menschen mit Behinderungen entsprechend ausgewiesen/gekennzeichnet? --- La segnaletica per l'orientamento e l'utilizzo della strutture è sufficiente? Il percorso di accesso consigliato per le persone con disabilità è adeguatamente identificato/segnalato? ---</p>		X	2.700,00	<p>- Der Zugang zur Struktur und der Eingangsbereich selbst sollten deutlich mit großen barrierefreien Hinweisschildern (mit großen, kontrastreichen Buchstaben und Symbolen) gekennzeichnet werden; - Die bodentiefen Verglasungen im Bürotrakt sollten mit einem kontrastreichen Streifen auf Augenhöhe deutlich gekennzeichnet werden; - Die Schließfächer sollten als Service groß und in kontrastreicher Schrift beschriftet werden; ---</p>

	Is the signage for orientation and use of the facilities sufficient? Is the recommended access route for persons with disabilities adequately identified/marked?				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - L'accesso alla struttura e l'area d'ingresso stessa dovrebbero essere segnalati con cartelli segnaletici senza barriere (con lettere e simboli grandi e ad alto contrasto); - Le vetrate a tutta altezza nell'ala degli uffici dovrebbero essere etichettate con una striscia ad alto contrasto all'altezza degli occhi; - Gli armadietti potrebbero essere etichettati come servizio con lettere grandi e ad alto contrasto; --- - Access to the structure and the entrance area itself should be clearly labelled with large barrier-free signs (with large, high-contrast letters and symbols); - The floor-to-ceiling glazing in the office wing should be clearly labelled with a high-contrast strip at eye level; - The lockers could be labelled as a service in large, high-contrast lettering;
53	<p>Hinweisschilder mit dem internationalen Rollstuhlzeichen/Benutzbarkeitssymbol weisen in angemessener Form auf Vorkehrungen hin, die für die Benutzbarkeit für Personen mit Behinderungen getroffen wurden?</p> <p>---</p> <p>La segnaletica riporta il contrassegno/pittogramma internazionale di accessibilità indicando in modo appropriato le disposizioni/accorgimenti previsti per l'accessibilità da parte di persone con disabilità?</p> <p>---</p> <p>Does the signage display the international accessibility symbol/pictogram appropriately indicating the provisions/accessibility measures for people with disabilities?</p>		X	50,00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In beiden Toiletten müsste das barrierefreie WC normgerecht mit dem internationalen Symbol für Vorkehrungen für Menschen mit Behinderungen gekennzeichnet werden; --- - In entrambi i servizi igienici, il bagno accessibile dovrebbe essere contrassegnato con il simbolo internazionale per le persone con disabilità; --- - In both toilets, the accessible toilet should be labelled with the international symbol for accommodations for people with disabilities in accordance with standards;
<p>Fluchtweg Via di fuga Escape route</p>					
53.5 54	<p>Gibt es einen normgerechten Fluchtweg?</p> <p>---</p> <p>Esiste una via di fuga a norma?</p> <p>---</p> <p>Is there a compliant escape route?</p>		X	9.000,00	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Im Küchenbereich sollte die verschlossene Tür mittels externer Manövrierfläche und seitlicher Rampe zu einem zusätzlichen barrierefreien Notausgang umfunktioniert werden (wodurch der ebene Vorplatz ferner als zugängliche Terrasse genutzt werden könnte); - Der Feuermelder im Eingangsbereich befindet sich in einer unzugänglichen Position und sollte uneingeschränkt zugänglich gemacht werden; --- - Nell'area della cucina, la porta chiusa dovrebbe essere trasformata in un'ulteriore uscita di emergenza accessibile, utilizzando uno spazio di

					<p>manovra esterno e una rampa laterale (che consentirebbe anche di utilizzare il piazzale pianeggiante come terrazza accessibile);</p> <p>- L'allarme antincendio nell'area d'ingresso è in una posizione inaccessibile e dovrebbe essere reso completamente accessibile;</p> <p>---</p> <p>- In the kitchen area, the closed door should be converted into an additional barrier-free emergency exit creating an external manoeuvring space and a ramp at the side (which would also allow the level forecourt to be used as an accessible terrace);</p> <p>- The fire alarm in the entrance area is in an inaccessible position and should be made fully accessible;</p>
<p>Summe Totale Total</p>				<p>67.000,0</p>	<p>Geschätzte Adaptierungskosten ---</p> <p>Costi di adattamento stimati ---</p> <p>Estimated adaptation costs</p>

2.1.3. Proposal for improvement

This section describes in greater detail specific improvements that are recommended to be made in the SuCoLo pilot site in Merano and its surrounding points of interest. In making these changes, accessibility can be ensured *for all*.

Maia Bassa railway station

The on-site survey demonstrated that the Merano-Maia Bassa railway station is accessible. The bus stops to reach the Merano-Maia Bassa railway station are located at the Maia Centre in Via delle Palade. The commuter car park at the station has parking spaces reserved for people with disabilities, several charging stations for electric cars and parking spaces for AlpsGo Carsharing South Tyrol.

The main entrance has steps. Therefore, there is an alternative accessible route without steps leading from the bus stops and the adjacent commuter car park on the left-hand side directly to platform 1, with an accessible raised platform. A level crossing also leads to platform 2, with an accessible raised platform.

The station building includes a waiting room (access requires a 5 cm threshold, doorway 62 cm wide), the café with tobacco shop (first entrance has a 3.5 cm threshold, second doorway has a width of 79 cm) and the toilets (men's toilet with sufficient space for a wheelchair user, without the necessary aids).

Figure 6 Maia Bassa railway station

Bus stop

The bus stop in the direction of the city centre is accessible. It has a raised stopping area (pedestrian pavement) and a covered waiting area with seating (bench without armrests). There is no tactile guideway for visually impaired persons.

The bus stop opposite out of the city, in the direction of Marlengo, is also accessible. It is equipped with a raised stopping area (pedestrian pavement) but no covered waiting area. Moreover, it is not equipped with tactile guideway for visually impaired passengers.

Figure 7 Bus stop in the direction of the city centre Figure 8 Bus stop in the direction of Marlengo

Proposal for improvement

Both bus stops should be brought to compliance and equipped with dynamic passenger information:

- The bus stop in the direction of the city centre should be equipped with a tactile orientation system for visually impaired passengers, integrated into a tactile guideway from the station to the racecourse (MIND). The bench should be equipped with armrests on the sides and in the middle, to make it easier for older people to sit and stand up and to prevent people from lying down.
- The bus stop in the out-of-town direction (towards Marlengo) should be equipped with a covered waiting area with a roof and a tactile orientation system for the orientation of visually impaired passengers, integrated at the same time into a tactile guideway from the railway station to the hippodrome (MIND).

Figure 9 Bus stop without bus bay

Figure 10 Bus stop with bus bay

Figure 11 Example bench with armrests

Figure 12 Accessible space in the waiting area

Figure 13 Attachment of timetable

Figure 14 Proposed Tactile path within the road crossing

Reserved parking spaces

There are no reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities in the immediate vicinity of the entrance (not designated nor signed).

Figure 15 Entrance of the MIND Centre

Proposal for improvement

Several compliant parking spaces for people with disabilities should be designated in the entrance area and signed accordingly with horizontal yellow floor marking and vertical sign. Additionally, the prospective parking spaces should be set up with accessible charging stations for electric vehicles and equipped with barrier-free charging columns.

In addition, future parking spaces for people with disabilities should be equipped with car park sensors from the [app Trova Parcheggi](#) (car park finder) to show visitors with disabilities their occupancy status in real time, i.e. whether the parking spaces are free or occupied.

Figure 16 Standardised design of reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities

Guidelines for creating accessible charging stations

- Level parking area: just like the reserved parking spaces for visitors with disabilities, accessible parking spaces should also be set up in an area that is as level as possible (maximum permitted slope < 5% and cross slope < 3%).
- Linear pavement: The parking spaces should have a linear pavement and no bumpy unevenness (e.g. grass, grass grid stones, loose gravel).
- Length 500 cm x width 350 cm (including 150 cm wide lateral marking of the free access area with hatching to ensure sufficient space for wheelchair users to get in and out of the vehicle). This minimum width considers that the loading bay can be on both sides of the vehicle (left-hand loader and right-hand loader).
- Regarding the minimum size of adjacent parking spaces (or in a herringbone pattern), as the preferred layout pattern for barrier-free charging stations, see figure A below.

Figure 17 Accessible charging station for electric cars

Entrance to the MIND Centre

The access path is mostly flat and has a beaten earth and compacted gravel pavement. Also, there is a bell with intercom in the entrance gate area of the racecourse, while there is no bell at the actual entrance door with house number 92A. Furthermore, the entrance door has a width of 70 cm + 70 cm. However, due to the emergency exit lever on the door, the width of the free passage is less. The second door leaf can only be opened with help. Even more, there is no tactile path for visually impaired persons to the entrance area (information desk/reception). Access to the MIND Centre and the entrance itself are not sufficiently signposted and are not recognisable as such for people with learning difficulties.

Figure 18 Entrance to the MIND Centre

Proposal for improvement

- The entrance with house number 92A should be equipped with a bell with intercom at a height of 90 cm.
- The entrance door is rather heavy and only partially accessible to wheelchair users due to its double-leaf design, which is why we recommend replacing it with an automatic sliding door if possible.
- The access path should be equipped with a tactile path for blind people. Access to the MIND Centre and the entrance area itself should be clearly marked with large accessible signs (with large high-contrast letters and symbols).

Indoor routes

Starting from the accessible entrance hall with the reception, all areas (coworking space, meeting rooms, kitchen, toilets) are accessible via a barrier-free ramp.

Figure 19 Indoor routes at the MIND Centre

Proposal for improvement

- The entrance area should be equipped with a tactile path from the door to the reception and a tactile map of MIND.
- The reception desk is 120 cm high and not wheelchair accessible, which is why there is a small accessible table right next to it as a barrier-free alternative. This should be replaced with a table with 4 corner table legs and labelled accordingly.
- The reception should be equipped with an induction system for hearing impaired people and this should be signposted accordingly for filling out forms.
- The ramp should be equipped with a compliant handrail on both sides.

Sanitary facilities at the MIND Centre

1. WC North

WC North has an accessible toilet for people with disabilities.

Figure 20 WC North at the MIND Centre

Proposal for improvement

- The toilet should be marked with the international symbol for provisions for people with disabilities.
- The pull cord of the alarm bell should be replaced with an appropriately longer pull cord that reaches down almost to the floor so that the alarm bell can also be triggered by a person who has fallen.
- One of the urinals should be lowered to a child-friendly height of 50 cm (beak height).
- Last but not least, the accessible toilet should be equipped with an accessible shelf and hanging hooks.

2. WC South

WC South has an accessible toilet for people with disabilities.

Figure 21 WC South – 77 cm door due to emergency exit lever

Figure 22 WC South – Changing table

Figure 23 WC South

Proposal for improvement

- The toilet should be marked with the international symbol for provisions for people with disabilities.
- The pull cord of the alarm bell should be replaced with an appropriately longer pull cord that reaches down almost to the floor so that the alarm bell can also be triggered by a person who has fallen.
- The accessible toilet should be equipped with a reachable shelf and hanging hooks.
- The free area by the washbasins on the far right could be converted into a safe changing table with a hygienic, soft base and easily accessible shelves and hanging hooks.

Elevator at the MIND Centre

There is no elevator. The building is designed at ground level. The two existing levels, which are offset in height, are accessible via a ramp in the entrance area.

Stairs at the MIND Centre

The steps have no tactile and high-contrast chromatic labelling and no handrail.

Figure 24 Stairs at the MIND Centre

Proposal for improvement

- The steps should be equipped with handrails on both sides according to UNI 10809 (installation height 95-105 cm).
- As there are 3 steps, in this case all 3 treads should be marked with a colour and material differentiation, for a depth of at least 5 cm, measured from the edge between tread and riser and across the entire width of the step.
- In addition, a tactile floor marker perceptible for blind or visually impaired people should be placed at least 30 cm from the first and last step to indicate the beginning and end of the ramp.

Complementary works at the MIND Centre

1. Parcel lockers

The 3rd row of lockers from the bottom with 6 compartments at an accessible operating height of 90 cm could be labelled as “Reserved for people with disabilities” with a sticker bearing the wheelchair pictogram. The corresponding compartment doors should be fitted with buttons on the fronts that are easy to touch.

Figure 25 Parcel lockers at the MIND Centre

2. Table and chairs

The **table and chairs** in the entrance area are only partially accessible for people with mobility and visual impairments due to the creative floor design and should be redesigned to be accessible for *all*.

Figure 26 Table and chairs in the entrance area

Figure 27 Inconvenient gravelled floor and wooden floorboards

3. Kitchen

The kitchen is accessible to people with disabilities, but not all parts can be used independently without barriers. For example, the kitchen furniture (sink and hob) is not wheelchair-accessible, and the existing high bistro tables are also not suitable, so at least one wheelchair-accessible table should be provided that can be used both for preparing food and eating.

Figure 28 Kitchen area

4. Floor to ceiling glass fronts

The floor to ceiling glass fronts in the corridor leading to the office wing is not sufficiently perceptible for the visually impaired and should therefore be clearly marked with a high-contrast strip at eye level.

Figure 29 Floor to ceiling glazing

Signage at the MIND Centre

The general findability (orientation) of the building is inadequate and should be improved with a barrier-free guidance concept.

Figure 30 The inadequate general findability/orientation to the building

Proposal for improvement

- The accessible toilets for people with disabilities should be signposted in accordance with standards.
- The lockers should be labelled large and in high-contrast lettering as a service.

Escape route at the MIND Centre

The escape routes are properly marked and labelled, as is the external assembly point.

Figure 31 Labelling of main entrance

Figure 32 Missing emergency exit in the kitchen area

Proposal for improvement

- In the kitchen area, the locked door could be converted into a barrier-free emergency exit, which would allow the level forecourt to be used as an accessible terrace.
- The fire alarm in the entrance area is in an inaccessible position: in addition to its unfavourable installation height (90 cm would be ideal), the existing gravel flooring in this area, as well as the high table and wastepaper basket, hinder barrier-free access to the fire alarm. The fire alarm should be made fully accessible.

2.2. Standardised adaptation plans in Leipzig

This section denotes the background and contextual factors concerning the research pilot site in Leipzig and its surrounding area, the on-site surveys taken, along with detailed recommendations for improvement to be fully accessible to *all* user groups.

2.2.1. Background

Lützschena-Stahmeln comprises the districts of Hänichen, Lützschena, Quasnitz and Stahmeln (with the old town centres and the industrial and commercial park). It is located on the White Elster river and New Luppe water channel and stretches along Hallesche Straße street and the White Elster river.

Lützschena-Stahmeln has road and rail connections. It is located on Federal Highway 6, the section of which runs from Halle to Leipzig. Tram line 11 connects the town with the city of Leipzig, and bus line 91 connects the freight transport centre. In addition, the district is crossed by the Leipzig-Wahren–Leipzig central station railway line, which provides half-hourly connections to Halle and Leipzig city centre via the Lützschena stop on the S3 line of the Central German S-Bahn (source: <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lützschena-Stahmeln>).

Figure 33 Map of Leipzig (with Lützschena framed in green) (Source: <https://www.openstreetmap.org>)

As part of the SuCoLo project, the car park at Lützschena Town Hall was selected as a strategic location for the mobile micro-hub. This location was chosen because the Lützschena district offers favorable conditions that make the operation and use of such a hub particularly sensible:

- Lützschena is located on the less well-connected outskirts of Leipzig and therefore offers great potential for innovative solutions in the field of sustainable logistics to make up for the area's lack of fixed service facilities. At the same time, the district is near Leipzig's freight transport centre, which includes Leipzig Airport, European Air Transport Leipzig and the World Cargo Centre Leipzig. This proximity enables efficient connections to supra-regional goods flows and promotes integration into existing logistics networks.
- Despite its peripheral location, Lützschena is well connected to public transport, both by tram and by buses as part of the rail replacement service (SEV) (see above). The selected location at the town hall is also characterised by its barrier-free accessibility and is easily accessible for all users.
- Another advantage is that the site is owned by the city of Leipzig, which ensures a stable institutional basis and close cooperation between public administration and the local economy. The mobile micro-hub also functions as a cooperation point where new models of sustainable urban logistics can be tested and jointly developed.
- Last but not least, the Lützschena district fits in with the concept of the "15-minute city": most everyday errands can be done within a 15-minute walk. This creates ideal conditions for neighbourhood-based and environmentally-friendly distribution of goods – a key goal of the SuCoLo project.

Furthermore, the Lützschena tram stop at Hallesche Straße street 107 was selected for the development of this adaptation plan for the removal of architectural barriers (PEBA) because it plays a very important role in the sustainable promotion of environmentally friendly local public transport in this peripheral district of Leipzig and because a forward-looking urban development project with many new accessible shops, offices and apartments is currently being built in its immediate vicinity on the large site of the former Sternburg Brewery.

Figure 34 Map section of the pilot district of Lützschena with transport connections, with the SuCoLo mobile micro-hub depicted (Source: <https://www.openstreetmap.org>)

Figure 35 Tram stop Lützschena analysed for PEBA (marked in green) (Source: Google Maps)

2.2.2. On-site survey

Table 2 On-site survey conducted at the tram and bus stop Lützschena (Leipzig)

Infrastrukturinstandhaltungskode: Codice manutenzione infrastruttura: Infrastructure maintenance code:			
Adresse: Indirizzo: Address:	Hallesche Straße 107 / Via Hallesche Straße 107 / Hallesche Straße Street 107		
BP.-Nr.: P. ed.: Building parcel no.:			
KG: C.C.: Cadastral municipality:			
Nutzungsart: Destinazione d'uso: Utilisation of the building:	Straßenbahnhaltstelle und Bushaltstelle für Schienenersatzverkehr / Fermata del tram e fermata dell'autobus per i servizi sostitutivi (SEV) / Tram stop and bus stop for rail replacement services (SEV)		
Baujahr und Datum Umbau: Anno di costruzione e data di ristrutturazione: Year of construction and date of renovation:			
Bestandsaufnahme bzgl. DLH 54 - 9 November 2009 (BZ) Stato attuale in rif. D.P.P. 54 - 9 novembre 2009 (BZ) Inventory regarding Decree of the provincial governor 54 – 9 November 2009 (BZ – Italy)	A	B	C
Geschätzte Kosten Costo stimato Estimated adaptation costs	Baukosten / Costo lavori / Adaptation costs in €: 159.500 Zur Verfügung stehende Beträge 35% in €: 55.825 Somme a disposizione 35% in €: 55.825 Available sums 35% in €: 55.825 GESAMTKOSTEN / TOTALE / TOTAL COSTS IN €: 215.325		
Für die Anpassung des Gebäudes laut DLH vom 09 November 2009 ist folgendes erforderlich Per l'adeguamento del fabbricato ai sensi del D.P.P. 09 novembre 2009 è necessario The following is required for the adaptation of the building according to the Decree of the President of the Province of Bolzano dated November 09 th 2009	Projekt <i>Progetto</i>	Baukonzession <i>Concessione Edilizia</i>	BBM <i>D.I.A.</i>

Der Techniker / Il Tecnico / The Technician	Erhebungsdatum / Data del rilevamento / Survey date: 16/07/2025 Magister Günther Ennemoser (IND)
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Artikel Articolo Article	Beschreibung Descrizione Description	Ja Sì Yes	Nein No No	Kosten € Costo € Costs €	Anmerkungen Osservazioni Notes
Reservierte Parkplätze für Menschen mit Behinderungen Parcheggi riservati per persone con disabilità Reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities					
22	Reservierte Parkplätze sind in erforderlicher Anzahl in der Nähe des Eingangs vorhanden? --- Sono presenti posti auto riservati per persone con disabilità in numero adeguato vicino all'ingresso? --- Are there an adequate number of reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities near the entrance?		X	4.500,00	In unmittelbarer Nähe zur Haltestelle gibt es keine reservierten Parkplätze für Menschen mit Behinderungen (nicht ausgewiesen oder entsprechend gekennzeichnet). - Schaffung von 3 asphaltierten normgerechten Behindertenparkplätzen auf dem gegenüberliegenden Parkplatz an der Ecke Hallesche Straße / Zur Alten Brauerei Straße. --- Non ci sono parcheggi riservati alle persone con disabilità nelle immediate vicinanze della fermata (non designati o segnalati). - Creazione di 3 parcheggi riservati per persone con disabilità asfaltati e conformi alle norme nel parcheggio di fronte, all'angolo tra via Hallesche Straße e via Zur Alten Brauerei. --- There are no reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities in the immediate vicinity of the tram station (not designated or signed). - Creation of 3 asphalted disabled parking spaces that comply with standards in the car park opposite, on the corner of Hallesche Straße street and Zur Alten Brauerei street.
	Fällt in die Zuständigkeit des Landes, der Gemeinde oder gilt etwas Anderes? --- Ricade nella competenza della provincia, del comune o altro? --- Does it fall under the competence of the province, the municipality or someone else?	X			Fällt in die Zuständigkeit der Gemeinde. --- Ricade nella competenza del comune. --- It falls within the competence of the municipality.
24	Befindet sich in unmittelbarer Nähe eine Bushaltestelle des öffentlichen Nahverkehrs? --- C'è una fermata dell'autobus pubblico nelle immediate vicinanze? --- Is there a public transport bus stop in the immediate vicinity?	X			Die Straßenbahnhaltestelle dient auch als Bushaltestelle für den Schienenersatzverkehr (SEV). --- La fermata del tram funge anche da fermata dell'autobus per il servizio sostitutivo (SEV). --- The tram stop also serves as a bus stop for rail replacement services (SEV).
53	Ist die vertikale und horizontale Beschilderung vorhanden? ---		X		Die horizontale Beschilderung (Bodenmarkierung) für die Bushaltestelle fehlt.

	<p>È presente la segnaletica verticale ed orizzontale? --- Is there vertical and horizontal signage?</p>				<p>--- Manca la segnaletica orizzontale (segnaletica sulla corsia) per la fermata dell'autobus. --- The horizontal signage (road markings) for the bus stop is missing.</p>
<p>Zugang zur Straßenbahnhaltestelle Accesso alla fermata del tram Access to the tram stop</p>					
33	<p>Der Zugang zur Straßenbahnhaltestelle ist selbstständig benutzbar? --- Il percorso alla fermata del tram è accessibile autonomamente? --- Is the access path to the tram station independently accessible?</p>		X	65.000	<p>Die Schienen verlaufen in der Straßenmitte. Es gibt auf beiden Seiten keine sichere barrierefreie Ein- und Ausstiegsplattform. - Barrierefreie Neugestaltung der gesamten Straßenbahnhaltestelle. --- I binari corrono al centro della strada. Su entrambi i lati non ci sono piattaforme per salire e scendere sicure e accessibili. - Rifacimento accessibile dell'intera fermata del tram. --- The tram tracks run down the middle of the road. There are no safe, barrier-free platforms for boarding and alighting on either side. - Barrier-free redesign of the whole tram stop.</p>
20	<p>Die vorhandenen Rampen sind normgemäß? --- Le rampe di accesso sono a norma? --- Are the access ramps compliant?</p>		X	3.000	<p>Die vorhandenen Gehsteigabsenkungen (Rampen) beim Fußgängerübergang mit akustischer Ampel in der Hallesche Straße sind normgerecht. Notwendige Adaptierungen: - Realisierung taktile Leitweg - Einzeichnung Zebrastreifen --- I raccordi del marciapiede con il piano stradale (rampe) presso l'attraversamento stradale con semaforo acustico in via Hallesche Straße sono conformi alle norme. Adattamenti necessari: - Realizzazione di percorsi tattili - Segnaletica orizzontale delle strisce pedonali --- The connections between the pavement and the road level (ramps) at the pedestrian crossing with acoustic traffic lights in Hallesche Straße street comply with the legal requirements. Necessary adaptations: - Implementation of tactile guidance system - Marking of zebra crossings</p>
34.6	<p>Der Wartebereich ist witterungsgeschützt, es gibt eine Überdachung? --- La zona di attesa è protetta dagli agenti atmosferici, è presente una tettoia? --- Is the waiting area protected from the weather, is there a roof?</p>		X	12.000	<p>Nur die Straßenbahnhaltestelle stadteinwärts hat einen überdachten Wartebereich. Dieser ist stufenlos zugänglich, hat eine barrierefreie Sitzbank mit seitlicher Armlehne und bietet neben der Sitzbank beidseitig einen überdachten Freiraum >90 cm für einen Kinderwagen oder Fahrgäste im Rollstuhl. Notwendige Adaptierungen:</p>

					<p>- Schaffung eines überdachten Wartebereichs für die Straßenbahnhaltestelle stadtauswärts.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Solo la fermata del tram in direzione centro città dispone di una zona di attesa coperta. Questa è accessibile senza gradini, dispone di una panchina accessibile con appoggiabraccia laterale e offre, su entrambi i lati della panchina, uno spazio coperto di oltre 90 cm per passeggini o viaggiatori in sedia a rotelle.</p> <p>Adattamenti necessari:</p> <p>- Creazione di un'area di attesa coperta per la fermata del tram in direzione periferia.</p> <p>---</p> <p>Only the tram stop heading into the centre has a covered waiting area. This is accessible without steps, has a barrier-free bench with side armrest and offers a covered space >90 cm on both sides of the bench for prams or passengers in wheelchairs.</p> <p>Necessary adaptations:</p> <p>- Creation of a covered waiting area for the tram stop heading towards the outskirts of the city.</p>
<p>Verbindungswege Percorsi di collegamento Connection paths</p>					
35.3	<p>Die Gehsteigbreite ist >1,50 m?</p> <p>---</p> <p>La larghezza del marciapiede è >1,50 m?</p> <p>---</p> <p>Is the pavement width >1.50 m?</p>	X			
48.1a	<p>Die Gehsteige sind niveaugleich, bzw. Schwellen sind <2,5 cm?</p> <p>---</p> <p>I marciapiedi sono allo stesso livello, ovvero le soglie sono <2,5 cm?</p> <p>---</p> <p>Are the pavements level (thresholds less than 2.5 cm high)?</p>	X			
47.3 + 53.3	<p>Gibt es eine taktile Bodenmarkierung?</p> <p>---</p> <p>È presente la segnaletica a pavimento tattile?</p> <p>---</p> <p>Is there tactile floor signage?</p>		X	15.000	<p>- Beidseitige Realisierung eines taktilen Leitweges und eines taktilen Übersichtsplans für die Straßenbahnhaltestelle.</p> <p>---</p> <p>- Realizzazione di un percorso guida e di una mappa tattile per la stazione delle tram su entrambi i lati.</p> <p>---</p> <p>- Realisation on both sides of a tactile guide path and a tactile map for the tram station.</p>
<p>Sanitäranlagen Servizi igienici Sanitary facilities</p>					
44	<p>Sind normgemäße sanitäre Anlagen vorhanden?</p> <p>---</p> <p>Esistono servizi igienici a norma?</p> <p>---</p>	X	X	60.000	<p>Es gibt keine Toilette.</p> <p>Im Bereich des angrenzenden Parkplatzes an der Ecke Hallesche Straße / Zur Alten Brauerei Straße könnte eine</p>

	Are there compliant barrier-free toilets? ---				selbstreinigende barrierefreie Familientoilette für <i>alle</i> geschaffen werden. --- Non ci sono servizi igienici. Nell'area del parcheggio adiacente all'angolo tra via Hallesche Straße e via Zur Alten Brauerei potrebbe essere realizzata una toilette autopulente per famiglie accessibile a <i>tutti</i> . --- There is no toilet. An accessible self-cleaning family restroom for <i>all</i> could be created in the adjacent car park area on the corner of Hallesche Straße street and Zur Alten Brauerei street.
44	Sind die sanitären Einrichtungen und das Zubehör normgemäß? --- Gli apparecchi sanitari e gli accessori sono a norma? --- Do sanitary appliances and accessories comply with standards?	/			
45	Sind normgemäße Duschen vorhanden? --- Esistono docce a norma? --- Are there showers that comply with standards?	/			
46	Gibt es einen zugänglichen Umkleideraum? (nur bei Gebäuden, wo ein solcher vorgesehen ist) --- Esiste lo spogliatoio accessibile? (solo per le strutture che lo prevedono) --- Is there an accessible changing room? (only for facilities that provide it)	/			
44 + 45 +46	Im Falle von mehreren Sanitäranlagen: In jeder vorhandenen Sanitärgruppe ist jeweils eine Sanitäranlage laut Art. 44, 45 und 46 vorhanden? --- In caso di più servizi igienici: In ogni gruppo di servizi igienici presente c'è un servizio ai sensi dell'art. 44, 45 e 46? --- In the case of several sanitary facilities: Is there in each group of sanitary facilities present a toilet according to Art. 44, 45 and 46?	X			
Aufzugsanlagen Impianti di sollevamento Escalator					
39	Gibt es einen Aufzug? --- Esiste un ascensore? ---	/			Die Haltestelle ist ebenerdig angelegt. Es braucht keinen Aufzug. ---

	Is there a lift?				La fermata è a livello del suolo. Non è necessario un ascensore. --- The tram stop is at ground level. No lift is required.
39	Entspricht der bestehende Aufzug den geltenden Vorschriften laut Art. 39 (im Schulneubau laut Art. 55 - Aufzugmaße, Türen, Bedientafel, Alarm usw.)? --- L'ascensore è a norma ai sensi dell'art. 39 (nell'edilizia scolastica ai sensi dell'art. 55 - dimensioni, porte, pulsantiera, allarme ecc.)? --- Is the lift compliant according to Art. 39 (in school buildings according to Art. 55 - dimensions, doors, push button panel, alarm, etc.)?	/			
40	Ist es notwendig, einen Treppenaufzug zu installieren? --- È necessario installare un servoscala? --- Is it necessary to install a stair lift?		/		
Treppen Scale Stairs					
36 - 37	Sind die Treppen, Stufen, Brüstungen, Handläufe normgemäß? --- Scale, gradini, parapetti, corrimano sono a norma? --- Are stairs, steps, parapets, handrails in compliance?	/			
37.1	Es gibt einen beidseitigen Handlauf entlang der Treppen? --- Su entrambi i lati delle scale è presente un corrimano? --- Is there a handrail on both sides of the stairs?	/			
37.2	Ist die Höhe des Handlaufs $0,95 < h < 1,05$ m und die der Brüstung $h = 1,00$ m? --- Il corrimano ha altezza $0,95 < h < 1,05$ m e il parapetto $h = 1,00$ m? --- Does the handrail have height $0.95 < h < 1.05$ m and the parapet $h = 1.00$ m?	/			
Komplementäre Arbeiten Opere complementari Complementary works					
51					

Beschilderung Segnaletica Signage					
53	<p>Die Beschilderung zur Orientierung und Benützung der baulichen Einrichtungen ist ausreichend? Der empfohlene Zugangsweg für Menschen mit Behinderungen entsprechend ausgewiesen/gekennzeichnet? ---</p> <p>La segnaletica per l'orientamento e l'utilizzo della strutture è sufficiente? Il percorso di accesso consigliato per le persone con disabilità è adeguatamente identificato/segnalato? ---</p> <p>Is the signage for orientation and use of the facilities sufficient? Is the recommended access route for persons with disabilities adequately identified/marked?</p>	X			
53	<p>Hinweisschilder mit dem internationalen Rollstuhlzeichen/Benutzbarkeitssymbol weisen in angemessener Form auf Vorkehrungen hin, die für die Benutzbarkeit für Personen mit Behinderungen getroffen wurden? ---</p> <p>La segnaletica riporta il contrassegno/pittogramma internazionale di accessibilità indicando in modo appropriato le disposizioni/accorgimenti previsti per l'accessibilità da parte di persone con disabilità? ---</p> <p>Does the signage display the international accessibility symbol/pictogram appropriately indicating the provisions/accessibility measures for people with disabilities?</p>	X			
Fluchtweg Via di fuga Escape route					
53.5 54	<p>Gibt es einen normgerechten Fluchtweg? ---</p> <p>Esiste una via di fuga a norma? ---</p> <p>Is there a compliant escape route?</p>	X			
Summe Totale Total				159.500	Geschätzte Adaptierungskosten --- Costi di adattamento stimati --- Estimated adaptation costs

2.2.3. Proposal for improvement

Lützschena tram stop

The Lützschena tram stop is located at Hallesche Straße street 107 / corner of Zur Alten Brauerei street and is not accessible for people with disabilities. The tram tracks run parallel in the middle of the street and are flanked on one side by a lane that separates the tram stops in the middle of the street from the safe pavement at the edge of the street. Furthermore, the tram stop does not have a raised platform, which would make it easier to get on and off and would enable families with prams, senior citizens and passengers in wheelchairs to use it. To get on and off, passengers must cross the road on one side, which is a daily hazard.

Figure 36 Lützschena tram stop heading out of city

Figure 37 Lützschena tram stop towards city centre

Proposal for improvement

The entire tram stop should be converted into a barrier-free tram stop in the middle, with two different types of stops (see model sketches below):

1. 'Tram stop at the edge of the road' on one side and
2. 'Tram stop as a protected time island with a raised track at the edge of the road' on the other side.

With this type of tram stop, passengers cross a raised lane when getting on and off, which requires signal protection in the form of a dynamic time island in the form of a traffic light system.

Figure 38 Type of stop 'tram stop at the edge of the road' with passenger shelter, side protection including ground indicators and dynamic information system – Source <https://barrierefreie-mobilitaet.de>

Figure 39 Type of stop 'tram stop as a protected time island with raised track at the edge of the road' with passenger shelter – source: initial sketch <https://barrierefreie-mobilitaet.de> – Project-specific modification by IND

Equipping the new stop in the central location with barrier-free access on both sides involves:

- Barrier-free elevation of the stop platform with a raised kerb on the side: The entry height of the city's low-floor trams is 25 cm to 30 cm above the top of the rails. This requires the use of special kerbs (special moulded blocks) and sufficiently long and straight access routes.
- As this stop is also served by buses in rail replacement service (SEV), a kerb is recommended for combined tram and bus access. Due to the different types of tram vehicles, there are various options for this. The high kerbs are often adapted to the vehicles of the respective transport company. Raised studs on the upper side increase slip resistance for passengers.
- Construction of a barrier-free passenger shelter on both sides with an accessible bench with armrests and sufficient covered space on the sides >150x150 cm for prams or passengers in wheelchairs.
- Standard-compliant design for visually impaired passengers in terms of tactile floor indicators, side protection and dynamic passenger information: At tram stops at the edge of the road, a locatability strip – in a ribbed structure parallel to the stop kerb – with a depth of 90 cm laid across the entire width of the pavement indicates the position of the first vehicle door towards the means of transport. The locatability strip connects to the boarding area, is 1.20 m wide parallel to the kerb and 90 cm deep. The distance to the kerb is 30 cm.

Figure 40 Realisation example “Tram stop as a protected time island with raised track at the edge of the road” Viaduktbögen street – Innsbruck (Austria)

Figure 41 Realisation example “Tram stop as a protected time island with raised track at the edge of the road” Claudiastraße street – Innsbruck (Austria)

Parking spaces

There are no reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities (not designated or marked accordingly) in the large gravel car park on Zur Alten Brauerei street, which is located in the immediate vicinity of the tram stop.

Figure 42 Large gravel car park on Zur Alten Brauerei street

Proposal for improvement

It is proposed to create at least three parking spaces reserved for people with disabilities next to the car access area or in the barrier-free access area at the tram stop, in accordance with regulations and marked with appropriate horizontal markings on the floor and vertical signs. The technical requirements for the creation of reserved parking spaces for people with disabilities in Germany (source: <https://nullbarriere.de>) are below:

- Disabled parking spaces with side exit: at least 3.50 m wide (free movement area) and at least 5.00 m long.

- Barrier-free access area: threshold-free access and barrier-free access to the pavement.
- Slope conditions: areas intended for pedestrian traffic must be designed in such a way that people with motoric impairments, in particular wheelchair and rollator users, can use them independently and safely. This also applies to areas around the car to prevent wheelchairs and rollators from drifting away. Parking spaces may only have a slight longitudinal slope of no more than 3% and a transverse slope of no more than 2%.
- Surface design: Movement areas and usable pavement widths must be level and low-vibration for barrier-free use. Bituminous and hydraulically bound surfaces are possible as level surface coverings, as are paving and slab coverings that are designed to meet at least the requirements of DIN 18318 [15]. These include: asphalt, concrete slabs, natural stone slabs (sawn), concrete paving stones (without chamfer, narrow joints or compacted or grouted), clinker and brick paving, natural stone paving (sawn, narrow joints or compacted or grouted).

Also, the parking spaces could be set up as accessible charging stations for electric vehicles and equipped with barrier-free charging columns. Guidelines for creating accessible charging stations are summarized below:

- Level parking area: just like the reserved parking spaces for visitors with disabilities, accessible parking spaces should also be set up in an area that is as level as possible (maximum permitted slope < 5% and cross slope < 3%).
- Linear pavement: The parking spaces should have a linear pavement and no bumpy unevenness (e.g. grass, grass grid stones, loose gravel).
- Length 500 cm x width 350 cm (including 150 cm wide lateral marking of the free access area with hatching to ensure sufficient space for wheelchair users to get in and out of the vehicle). This minimum width considers that the loading bay can be on both sides of the vehicle (left-hand loader and right-hand loader).
- Regarding the minimum size of adjacent parking spaces (or in a herringbone pattern), as the preferred layout pattern for barrier-free charging stations, see figure A below.

Figure 43 Sketch of an accessible charging station for electric cars

Lastly, if a parking spot for cars is built in the future, then it is recommended that the access route from the car park to the tram stop should be equipped with a tactile guidance system.

Figure 44 Access route from the car park to the tram stop that could potentially be equipped with a tactile guidance system

Sanitary facilities

Apart from the small visitor centre Auwaldstation, there are no public toilets in the entire district of Lützschena-Stahmeln.

Proposal for improvement

It would be beneficial for sustainable district development to build a self-cleaning, barrier-free family restroom for *all* next to this central tram stop in the publicly accessible car park area on Zur Alten Brauerei Straße.

This toilet should be suitable for use by both parents and children and should be equipped with two toilets and washbasins: one toilet and washbasin in child size and one toilet and washbasin in adult size. The adult toilet should be completely accessible for people with disabilities and therefore equipped with the necessary accessories. The adult washbasin should be suitable in size and design for washing a baby; next to the washbasin, there should be a folding changing table with appropriate storage space.

Figure 45 *Proposal for improvement: the creation of an accessible family restroom*

Elevator

There is no elevator. The building is designed at ground level. The two existing levels, which are offset in height, are accessible via a ramp in the entrance area.

Complementary works

Only the tram stop towards the centre has a covered waiting area and this is located quite far from the actual stop. The tram shelter is accessible without steps, has a barrier-free bench with side armrest and offers a covered space >90 cm on both sides of the bench for prams or passengers in wheelchairs.

Figure 46 Covered waiting area near the tram stop

Proposal for improvement

A covered waiting area for the tram stop heading towards the outskirts of the city can be created.

Figure 47 Example bench with armrests

Figure 48 Accessible space in the waiting area

Figure 49 Attachment of timetable

Signage

The signage is adequate.

Escape Route

The proposed barrier-free redesign of the tram stop will also eliminate the danger zone in the boarding and alighting area of the road to be crossed.

3. Conclusion and outlook

The georeferenced mapping of POIs regarding accessibility and standardised adaptation plans (PEBA) presented in this deliverable demonstrate that the main points of interest in both SuCoLo pilot sites - the MIND Centre in Merano and the Lützschena tram stop in Leipzig - offer a promising basis for inclusive, barrier-free infrastructure that supports sustainable mobility around the sites. The detailed on-site surveys revealed several areas in which accessibility is already ensured, alongside a number of targeted interventions required to meet national and international standards to make the areas accessible for *all*. These improvements range from optimising entrances and indoor routes to enhancing signage, sanitary facilities, and public transport connections.

The georeferenced mapping of points of interest - known as the geospatially referenced locations that have functional, social, or economic relevance to users of that site - has proven to be a powerful tool for identifying not only the current state of accessibility but also opportunities for integration with other mobility forms. By visualising these POIs and linking the most pertinent ones to concrete adaptation measures, the project provides municipalities, planners, and citizens with a transparent and actionable overview of accessibility status. Its modular architecture, along with a developers' guide to integrate a POI plug-in on a content management system enables replication and adaption to fit other contexts.

The methodological framework developed here can be applied to other circumstances beyond the SuCoLo project. Looking ahead, the prospective implementation of the proposed measures would not only improve the physical accessibility of the sites but also contribute to social inclusion and environmental sustainability. Future work will focus on refining the georeferenced POI plug-in and sharing best practices across other regions, which will be apparent in the SuCoLo *Toolkit for bicycle hubs & sustainable logistics in urban outskirts* (D4.4). By embedding accessibility considerations into all stages of planning and design, SuCoLo will help ensure that its sustainable logistics solutions are truly for *all*.

Appendix

1. Developers' guide: Structure of the georeferenced POIs plug-in and adapting it to various content management systems

This documentation has been created for developers and can be used to understand how this plug-in is structured and how to customize it by adapting it to the various Content Management Systems (CMS) currently in use. This guide outlines the folders used, the main configuration files, CMS menu integration, adding new languages, the front-end widget, marker customization, classes and functions, and database tables. To access the file that holds the plug-in and to access the developers' guide in Italian and German, please refer to SuCoLo's open access repository:

SuCoLo open access repository:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/sucolo/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

What you should already know

This documentation assumes you have some basic background, including good working knowledge of

- HyperText Markup Language Language (HTML)
- Cascading Style Sheets (CSS)
- Javascript
- HyperText Preprocessor (PHP)
- Extended Markup Language (XML)

MySQL knowledge is required if you want to add new data fields.

What does this document not include

This documentation does not contain information related to any CMS. Each CMS has its own system with which it imports plug-ins made by third parties. You will have to retrieve all the information necessary to understand how to adapt the IT TOOL configuration files to the CMS you want to use.

Document conventions

This documentation uses absolute representations of paths based on the root element of the IT TOOL, eg.

`/lib/class_SYS_global.php`

Following font conventions are used:

- The monospace font is used for sample code and code listings, language elements (such as variables and function params), filenames, directory names and HTML tags.
- *Italic type* is used for titles and emphasis.

Folder used

In this chapter we will introduce the folder used in this IT TOOL:

/css

Contains all Cascading Style Sheet files used within the IT TOOL.

/etc

Contains all configuration files.

/fonts

Contains all included third party font files (eg. font-awesome).

/frontend

Contains the widget main file widget.php that should be used in the front end to show IT TOOL contents.

/img

Contains images used within the entire IT TOOL.

/js

Contains all Javascript files used within the IT TOOL.

/lib

Contains the files with classes definitions included in the main php files.

/lng

Contains all languages directories. Languages directories are named with the language code (eg. it, de, en) and contains all the translated xml files of the text used within the IT TOOL.

/media

The media folder is used to contain media files uploaded by the user. The main folder located within the media folder is domain_1 where 1 indicates the id of the related domain. Here you can find the folders related to the IT TOOL module parts POI_categories and POI_points where the uploaded medias will be placed.

/media/domain_{n}/POI_categories

Contains a folder for each created category named with the id of the category. The uploaded media file is called logo and has the file extension of the uploaded file, eg. logo.png. This file should be used as offline media file. By publishing the category a new file with _pub suffix will be created, eg. logo_pub.png. This last file should be used for front end purpose.

/media/domain_{n}/POI_points

Contains a folder for each created point of interest named with the id of the point. The uploaded media file is called image and has the file extension of the uploaded file, eg. image.jpg. This file should be used as offline media file. By publishing the point a new file with _pub suffix will be created, eg. image_pub.jpg. This last file should be used for front end purpose.

/prg

Contains all main php files used by the IT TOOL. Suffix main is used to indicate the start point of the module, eg. POI_categories_main.php, suffix form is used to indicate the form to create new entries or modify already existing ones, eg. POI_categories_form.php, and suffix sql is used to indicate where sql operations are done normally used within an Ajax call, eg. POI_categories_sql.php.

The php files without suffix, POI_categories.php and POI_points.php, should be used to call the modules from within your own CMS menu.

/prg/menu

Here you can find php files that will be included as lateral menu of the related main php file located in /prg.

Main configuration files

In this chapter we will introduce the main IT TOOL configuration files and how they must be adapted to your system.

/etc/config.php

The IT TOOL doesn't use the database connection of the CMS but has its own. For this reason it is necessary to configure access to the database by filling in the following lines.

```
$cms_global->db_host = "{your host}";
```

```
$cms_global->db_port = "3306";
```

```
$cms_global->db_username = "{your username}";
```

```
$cms_global->db_password = "{your password}";
```

```
$cms_global->db_name = "{your database}";
```

<pre>\$cms_global->db_host</pre>	The MySQL server is normally located within the main web server. Therefore localhost is the common value used. Otherwise you have to indicate the host of the MySQL server by entering the right ip address.
<pre>\$cms_global->db_port</pre>	The default port of MySQL servers is 3306. Change this value
<pre>\$cms_global->db_username</pre>	Indicates the username for MySQL connection.
<pre>\$cms_global->db_password</pre>	Indicates the password for MySQL connection.
<pre>\$cms_global->db_name</pre>	Enter the name of your database here.

Then you have to define the database table prefix, id of the domain to use and the id of the logged in user.

```
$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_table_prefix'] = '{your db table prefix}';
```

```
$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_id_domain'] = 1;
```

```
$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_id_user'] = 1;
```

<pre>\$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_table_prefix']</pre>	Enter database table prefix here, eg. _wp.
<pre>\$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_id_domain']</pre>	If your CMS supports multiple domain management, you can indicate the id of the domain to use here. If not sure, leave 1 as indicated.
<pre>\$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_id_user']</pre>	You have to indicate the id of the user logged in (normally passed as a session variable). If you don't know how to do this, leave 1 as indicated.

In the last part of this configuration file you can define the languages to use: the language or languages to use for front end content and the language used to interact with the CMS user.

```
$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_languages'] = array(
    1 => array('tid' => 1, 'sigle' => 'it', 'name' => 'italiano'),
```

```
2 => array('tid' => 2, 'sigle' => 'de', 'name' => 'deutsch')
);
$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_used_languages'] = array(1,2);
$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_system_language'] = 1;
```

`$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_languages']` The languages for which the CMS should be enabled must be configured as an associative array. `tid` indicates the id of the language for subsequent references. `sigle` indicates the folder which must be present in the `/lng` folder and which must contain all the files relating to the respective language. We will discuss how to add new languages later. `name` is the string used to identify the language within the plug-in.

`$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_used_languages']` You have to indicate all languages you will be able to use for the front end by entering the ids of the languages as values of an array. The ids must match the `tid` field configured in the previous associative array.

`$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_system_language']` You have to indicate the language to use within the CMS to interact with the user. The id must match the `tid` field configured in the previous associative array.

/etc/SYS_init.php

You have to indicate absolute and relative filesystem position on the server and URL of the plug-in main folder reachable from the CMS.

```
$plugin_relative = '{relative filesystem position}';
$plugin_dir_path = '/htdocs/testwp/wordpress/wp-content/plugins/IT_TOOL';
$plugins_url = 'http://localhost/testwp/wordpress/wp-content/plugins/IT\_TOOL';
```

<code>\$plugin_relative</code>	The relative filesystem position to the main folder of the plug-in based on the PHP file of the CMS that includes the plug-in.
<code>\$plugin_dir_path</code>	The absolute filesystem position to the main folder of the plug-in.
<code>\$plugins_url</code>	URL to the main folder of the plug-in.

The configuration of the elements shown could be as follows:

```
$plugin_relative = '../wp-content/plugins/IT_TOOL';  
$plugin_dir_path = '/htdocs/wordpress/wp-content/plugins/IT_TOOL';  
$plugins_url = 'https://localhost/plugins/IT\_TOOL';
```

CMS menu integration

In your CMS main menu you should have two entries: one for the category and the other for the points of interest module. In most of the third party CMS modules are included within an existing HTML page. To create a sort of root-directory of the IT TOOL we decided to load the main parts of the single modules using an `<iframe>`.

The CMS used should have a directory for plug-ins. This directory path should replace

`{cms_plugins_path}` indicated in the following paths.

Categories

To include the category module you have to create a link that points to the following php file

`{cms_plugins_path}/IT_TOOL/prg/POI_categories.php`

Points of interest

To include the points of interest module you have to create a link that points to the following php file

`{cms_plugins_path}/IT_TOOL/prg/POI_points.php`

Adding new languages

You have the possibility to manage two types of languages: languages to be used for displaying content in the front end and languages to be used to interact with the user (system languages).

Front end languages

To add a new language to be used for displaying content in the front end you have to do two things in the `/etc/config.php` file:

- add a new entry to the associative array `$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_languages']`, and
- indicate that you will use the language by adding the new tid to the

`$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_used_languages']` array.

If you want, for example, to add spanish as a new language you can modify the indicated arrays as follows:

```
$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_languages'] = array(
1 => array('tid' => 1, 'sigle' => 'it', 'name' => 'italiano'),
2 => array('tid' => 2, 'sigle' => 'de', 'name' => 'deutsch'),
3 => array('tid' => 3, 'sigle' => 'es', 'name' => 'Espagnol')
);
$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_used_languages'] = array(1,2,3);
```

Now the IT TOOL should gives you the possibility to add italian, german and spanish front end content.

System languages

To add a new system language you have to follow the indicated steps:

- Copy an existing language folder from within `/lng`, eg. `en`, to the same `/lng` folder and rename it to the new language sigle you need, eg. `es`.
- Translate the content of the xml files included in the new created language folder.
- Add a new entry to the associative array `$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_languages']` in the `/etc/config.php` file, if it not exists yet.
- Change the system language to use by indicating the right language id as the value of `$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_system_language']` in the `/etc/config.php` file.

Every xml file within the language folder has a structure like this

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
```

```
<translates>
<item id="title">Categories</item>
...
</translates>
```

where every <item> tag contains the string to use by indicating the associated id (in this case title). The string to translate is the one between <item> and </item> tags. The id attribute value must remain unchanged.

Front end widget

To include the IT TOOL widget within your own front end page you have to create an <iframe> tag in which the widget will be loaded. You can create the <iframe> tag like this

```
<iframe src="{url_to_cms_plugins}/IT_TOOL/frontend/widget.php? mode={mode}&
language={language_id}& latitude={lat_coord}& longitude={long_coord}" style="border:0;
width:800px; height:600px"></iframe>
```

As you can see different elements could be used to obtain the desired output. You should replace {url_to_cms_plugins} with the public URL that points to CMS plug-ins directory. The elements you can pass as GET variables are as follows:

mode	list to show list of publicated points of interest. Use map to show the OpenStreetMap positioned to the given latitude (lat_coord) and longitude (long_coord) coordinates
language_id	Id of the language to use based on the \$GLOBALS['IT_TOOL_languages'] variable set in the /etc/config.php file.
lat_coord	Latitude coordinate to use for start position in map mode.
long_coord	Longitude coordinate to use for start position in map mode.

The style attribute of the <iframe> tag is used as online style but should be replaced by a style class.

Here are some Wordpress examples:

```
<iframe src="https://www.testwp.lan/wordpress/wp-
content/plugins/IT_TOOL/frontend/widget.php?mode=list&language=1"
style="border:0;width:800px; height:600px"></iframe>
```

to show content in list mode, or

<iframe src="https://www.testwp.lan/testwp/wordpress/wp-content/plugins/IT_TOOL/frontend/widget.php?mode=map&language=1&latitude=46.6712938&longitude=11.1525179" style="border:0;width:800px; height:600px"></iframe>
to show content in map mode.

Marker customization

As marker we intend the image added to a category and shown as a placeholder within the Open Street Map. It is possible to customize the design of category marker but you have to follow some default settings.

The following image shows a possible marker.

The marker must have a width of 36 pixels and a height of 48 pixels. The pointer indicates the point where the marker is positioned at the map coordinates and should be in the middle of the bottom side.

The marker must have a width of 36 pixels and a height of 48 pixels. The pointer indicates the point where the marker is positioned at the map coordinates and should be in the middle of the bottom side.

Classes and functions

This chapter contains the list of classes with the related functions present in the IT TOOL plug-in. The specifications shown can be used for future customizations.

class_POI_categories.php

Class to manage categories within the IT TOOL plug-in. The private variables defined within this class are:

`$id_user` Id of the CMS user.

\$id_language	Id of the system language to use.
\$tid	Table id of the category.
\$visible	Indicates whether the category should be visible or not in the front end.
\$file_img_logo	Contains \$_FILE object passed by the filled out HTML form.
\$name	Defined as array where the key of the array entry is the language id and the value the name of the category in the given language.
\$json	JSON structure used to pass more items to be modified or deleted.
\$arr_languages	Array of the defined languages.
\$offline	Defines whether to extract offline (true) or publicated (false) content. By default this variable is set to true (returns offline content).
\$media_folder_url	URL to the folder used to save media files for this object.
\$allowed_file_ext	Array with allowed file extension for image upload. By default you can upload jpg, png and jpeg files.

function getPublicatedContent();
Switch from offline content to publicated content.

function getMediaFolderUrl();
Return media folder url.
Return

String Media folder url

function getCategories(\$params);
Returns array with all entries. Value of field pub_status is used to indicate wether the category is not publicated (1), revisioned, but not publicated (2), or publicated (3).
Params passed as associative array

show_deleted true to include deleted categories, otherwise false.

Return

Array List of all entries.

function getCategory(\$tid);
Returns array of desired entry. Params

\$tid
Return Table id of the category to return.

Array Associative array with all fields of the category identified by passed table id.

function loadRequestVariables();

This method loads passed \$_REQUEST variables.

function save();

Checks whether to do an insert or an update and processes the right sql operation. Return

String OK if sql was processed without errors, otherwise returns msg_error_required if required fields are empty, msg_error_prepare if an error occurred preparing sql statement or msg_error_execute if an error occurred executing sql statement.

function changeFieldStatus(\$field); Changes the status of given field. Params

\$field
Return Database table field to change status for.

String OK if sql was processed without errors, otherwise returns msg_error_required if required fields are empty, msg_error_prepare if an error occurred preparing sql statement or msg_error_execute if an error occurred executing sql statement.

function changePublicated(\$params);

Changes the publicated status of the entry. Params as associative array

tid
Return Table id of the category to publicate.

String OK if sql was processed without errors, otherwise returns msg_error_required if required fields are empty, msg_error_prepare if an error occurred preparing sql statement or msg_error_execute if an error occurred executing sql statement.

function multiChangePublicated();

Publicates elements passed as json list.

Return

String OK if sql was processed without errors, otherwise returns msg_error_required if required fields are empty, msg_error_prepare if an error occurred preparing sql statement or msg_error_execute if an error occurred executing sql statement.

function delete();

Deletes elements passed as json list. Return

String OK if sql was processed without errors, otherwise returns msg_error_required if required fields are empty, msg_error_prepare if an error occurred preparing sql statement or msg_error_execute if an error occurred executing sql statement.

class_POI_points.php

Class to manage categories within the IT TOOL plug-in. The private variables defined within this class are:

\$id_user	Id of the CMS user.
\$id_language	Id of the system language to use.
\$text	Contains the constant language text to use within this object.
\$tid	Table id of the point.
\$visible	Indicates whether the point should be visible or not in the front end.
\$id_category	Table id of the category to use.
\$rating	Rating value of the point.
\$lat	Latitude coordinate.
\$lng	Longitude coordinate.
\$youtube_code	Youtube code to include Youtube video.
\$vr_link	Link to virtual reality content for the point.
\$web	URL to the webpage.
\$email	Email address.

\$phone	Phone number.
\$services	Contains id of flagged accessibility services.
\$file_img	Contains \$_FILE object passed by the filled out HTML form.
\$title	Defined as array where the key of the array entry is the language id and the value the title of the point in the given language.
\$address	Defined as array where the key of the array entry is the language id and the value the address of the point in the given language.
\$description	Defined as array where the key of the array entry is the language id and the value the description of the point in the given language.
\$accessibility	Defined as array where the key of the array entry is the language id and the value the accessibility description of the point in the given language.
\$notes	Defined as array where the key of the array entry is the language id and the value the notes of the point in the given language.
\$json	JSON structure used to pass more items to be modified or deleted.
\$arr_languages	Array of the defined languages.
\$offline	Defines whether to extract offline (true) or publicated (false) content. By default this variable is set to true (returns offline content).
\$media_folder_url	URL to the folder used to save media files for this object.
\$allowed_file_ext	Array with allowed file extensions for image upload. By default you can upload jpg, png and jpeg files.
function setText(\$text); Set text language array. Params	

`$text` Array with constant text definitions for this object.

`function getPublicatedContent();`
Switch from offline content to publicated content.

function getMediaFolderUrl();

Return media folder url.

Return

String Media folder url

function getPoints(\$params);

Returns array with all entries. Value of field `pub_status` is used to indicate wether the point is not publicated (1), revisioned, but not publicated (2), or publicated (3).

Params passed as associative array

`show_deleted` true to include deleted points, otherwise false.
Return

Array List of all entries.

function getPoint(\$tid);

Returns array of desired entry. Params

`$tid` Table id of the point to return.

Return

Array Associative array with all fields of the point identified by passed table id.

function loadRequestVariables();

This method loads passed `$_REQUEST` variables.

function save();

Checks whether to do an insert or an update and processes the right sql operation.

Return

String OK if sql was processed without errors, otherwise returns `msg_error_required` if required fields are empty, `msg_error_prepare` if an error occured preparing sql statement or `msg_error_execute` if an error occured executing sql statement.

function changeFieldStatus(\$field); Changes the status of given field. Params

`$field` Database table field to change status for.

Return

String OK if sql was processed without errors, otherwise returns msg_error_required if required fields are empty, msg_error_prepare if an error occurred preparing sql statement or msg_error_execute if an error occurred executing sql statement.

function changePublicated(\$params); Changes the publicated status of the entry. Params as associative array

tid Table id of the point to publicate.
Return

String OK if sql was processed without errors, otherwise returns msg_error_required if required fields are empty, msg_error_prepare if an error occurred preparing sql statement or msg_error_execute if an error occurred executing sql statement.

function multiChangePublicated(); Publicates elements passed as json list. Return

String OK if sql was processed without errors, otherwise returns msg_error_required if required fields are empty, msg_error_prepare if an error occurred preparing sql statement or msg_error_execute if an error occurred executing sql statement.

function delete();

Deletes elements passed as json list.

Return

String OK if sql was processed without errors, otherwise returns msg_error_required if required fields are empty, msg_error_prepare if an error occurred preparing sql statement or msg_error_execute if an error occurred executing sql statement.

function loadDetailsPanel(\$tid);

Load point details panel to use for the front end.

Params

\$tid Table id of point to load details panel for.

class_SYS_database.php

Class that manages mysqli database connection. The constants defined within this class are:

<code>SYS_database::SELECT</code>	To define a select query.
<code>SYS_database::INSERT</code>	To define an insert statement.
<code>SYS_database::UPDATE</code>	To define an update statement.
<code>SYS_database::DELETE</code>	To define a delete statement.

The private variables defined within this class are:

<code>\$mode</code>	Identifies the mode indicated by one of the defined constants.
<code>\$db</code>	Database connection object.
<code>\$statement</code>	Statement object.

The public variables defined within this class are:

<code>\$connect_error</code>	Contains the string returned by the database object if an error occurred.
<code>\$error</code>	Contains the string returned by the statement object if an error occurred.

function isConfigured();

To check if database was configured properly.

Return

Boolean	true if database is configured properly, otherwise false.
---------	---

function selectDB(\$db_name); To select database to connect to. Params

<code>\$db_name</code>	Name of the database.
------------------------	-----------------------

function closeDB();

To close database connection.

function query(\$query);

This method processes a standard query. Params

<code>\$query</code>	MySQL query to process.
----------------------	-------------------------

Return

Object	Result object of the processed query.
--------	---------------------------------------

function execute();

This method processes a previously prepared query.

function free();

To free memory.

Return

Object	Result object returned by standard free() mysqli function.
--------	--

function fetchObject(\$result);

Returns fetched rows as an object array. Params

\$result	Returned result object.
----------	-------------------------

Return

Object	Result object returned by standard fetch_object() mysqli function.
--------	--

function fetchAssoc(\$result);

Returns fetched rows as an associative array. Params

\$result	Returned result object.
----------	-------------------------

Return

Array	Array returned by standard fetch_assoc() mysqli function.
-------	---

function fetchRow(\$result);

Returns fetched rows as an enumerated array. Params

\$result	Returned result object.
----------	-------------------------

Return

Array	Array returned by standard fetch_row() mysqli function.
-------	---

function getRows(\$result);

Returns fetched rows as selected array type. Object is the default type. Params

\$result	Returned result object.
\$type	Assoc for associative array, Object for objects and Row for enumerated array.

Return

Mix	Result based on indicated type param.
-----	---------------------------------------

function numRows(\$result); Returns number of rows. Params

`$result` Returned result object.
Return

`Int` Integer returned by standard `num_rows()` mysqli function.

function lastId(\$result);

Returns last id in case of `auto_increment`. Params
`$result` Returned result object.

Return

`Int` Integer returned by standard `insert_id()` mysqli function.

function affectedRows(\$result); Returns number of affected rows. Params

`$result` Returned result object
Return

`Int` Integer returned by standard `affected_rows()` mysqli function.

function prepareSELECT(\$query,\$bind_array);

This method prepares a select query for prepared statements. Params
`$query` Query to process with ? instead of values.

`$bind_array` Multi-dimensional array. Every entry consists of an array with table field name as key. The field array consists of two parts: type to identify the value type (s for string, i for integer, d for double and b for byte) and value that contains the value to pass.

function prepareINSERT(\$table,\$bind_array);

This method prepares an insert query for prepared statements.
Params

`$table` Table name where to insert the values.

`$bind_array` Multi-dimensional array. Every entry consists of an array with table field name as key. The field array consists of two parts: type to identify the value type (s for string, i for integer, d for double and b for byte) and value that contains the value to pass.

function prepareUPDATE(\$table,\$where,\$set_bind_array,\$where_bind_array);

This method prepares an update query for prepared statements.

Params

\$table	Table name where to insert the values.
\$where	Where block to use with ? instead of values
\$set_bind_array	Multi-dimensional array to use for set block. Every entry consists of an array with table field name as key. The field array consists of two parts: type to identify the value type (s for string, i for integer, d for double and b for byte) and value that contains the value to pass.
\$where_bind_array	Multi-dimensional array to use for where block. Every entry consists of an array with table field name as key. The field array consists of two parts: type to identify the value type (s for string, i for integer, d for double and b for byte) and value that contains the value to pass.

function prepareDELETE(\$table,\$where,\$bind_array);

This method prepares a delete query for prepared statements. Params

\$table	Table name where to insert the values.
\$where	Where block to use with ? instead of values
\$bind_array	Multi-dimensional array. Every entry consists of an array with table field name as key. The field

array consists of two parts: type to identify the value type (s for string, i for integer, d for double and b for byte) and value that contains the value to pass.

function autocommit(\$value);

Manage automatic commit of the database engine.

Params

\$value	true to activate automatic commit, false to deactivate it.
---------	--

function commit();

To fix sql operations in a transaction.

function rollback();

To rollback sql operations in a transaction.

function writeLog(\$method,\$message);

This method interrupt execution and shows the given message.

Params

\$method	Name of the method where the error occurred.
\$message	Text to show as error message.

class_SYS_global.php

This class contains global methods to use within entire module.

function strip(\$value);

This method un-quotes a quoted string or an array with quoted strings. Params

\$value	Quoted string or array of quoted strings to un-quote.
---------	---

Return

Mix	Un-quoted string or array with u-quoted strings.
-----	--

function getSession(\$name,\$default);

Returns a session variable. Params

\$name	Session variable key to return.
\$default	Value to return if session variable is not set.

Return

Mix	Value of the session variable.
-----	--------------------------------

function setSession(\$name,\$value);

Sets the value for a session variable.

Params

\$name	Session variable key to set.
\$value	Value to use to set session variable.

function getPost(\$name,\$default); Returns a \$_POST variable. Params

`$name` `$_POST` variable key to return.
`$default` Value to return if `$_POST` variable is not set.

Return

Mix Value of the `$_GET` variable.

function `getGet($name,$default)`;

Returns a `$_GET` variable. Params

`$name` `$_GET` variable key to return.
`$default` Value to return if `$_GET` variable is not set.

Return

Mix Value of the `$_GET` variable.

function `getRequest($name,$default)`; Returns a `$_REQUEST` variable. Params

`$name` `$_REQUEST` variable key to return.
`$default` Value to return if `$_REQUEST` variable is not set.

`class SYS_system.php`

This class is an extension of the global class `SYS_global` and contains module system related methods.

function `getModuleText($params)`;

This method returns the module text elements in the required language. Params as associative array

<code>sigle</code>	Language identifier, eg. it, de, en.
<code>module</code>	Name of the file to load within the respective language folder removing the file extension (.xml), eg. <code>POI_categories_main</code> .
<code>without-js</code>	By default it will be created the Javascript object <code>cms_TEXT</code> containing all loaded entries. By setting this parameter to true Javascript object will not be created.

Return

Array Loaded module text.

function getQueryStringArray();

Returns an associative array based on the query string of the actual URL.

Return

Array Key/value-Array representation of the query string.

function getQueryStringByArray(\$params);

Returns a query string based on a given array. Params

\$params Associative array where key is param name and value is the value of the param name.

Return

String String formed as query string (eg. key1=value1&key2=value2...).

function getLink(\$page,\$params);

This method returns the link to a requested page.

Params

\$page Page to load.

\$params Associative array of param name and param value pairs (eg. array('tid' => 1, 'nr' => 8)).

Return

String Link to requested page.

function getSystemLanguages();

Returns an array with system languages based on existing language folders where the language id is set as array key and language name as array value.

Return

Array Array with language id and language value pairs.

function loadLanguagesToolbar(\$params);

Shows languages toolbar within the module based on the used languages for the actual domain and languages set for the entire system.

Params as associative array

used_languages Array of languages ids used for the actual domain.

languages Array of languages ids set for the entire system.

function getSelectedToolbarLanguages();

Returns the value of the session variable cms_langToolbar which is set when language buttons are selected.

Return

String Language ids separated by pipe (eg. 1|2 – indicates that language 1 and 2 are active).

function loadHTML(\$params);

This method adds html header part and creates a <div> container.

Params as associative array

title Title to use within <title> tag.

styles Array of style-Files to load.

scripts Array of scripts-Files to load.

function loadFooter();

<div> tag for load animation and <div> tag for modal dialog box are added here before <body> and <html> tag are closed.

class_USR_permissions.php

This class is used to check user permissions.

function getPermission(\$params);

This method returns true if the logged in user has permission and false if not based on a given module name and one of the following permission

types: R –

read permission, W – write permission, D – delete permission.

Params as associative array

module	Name of the module to check permission for.
perm	Permission type (R – read permission, W – write permission, D – delete permission).
Return	
Boolean	true if the logged in user has permission and false if not.

Database tables

Necessary database tables are introduced in this chapter. There are two tables for every module. The tables `POI_categories_off` and `POI_categories_pub` are respectively used to contain offline and publicated entries of the categories module. `POI_points_off` and `POI_points_pub` are used to contain offline and publicated entries of the points module.

Every table contains one or more language fields. A language field must be added to the table for every added language used.

In the next MySQL code charset UTF-8 for entire database is assumed.

POI_categories_off

The MySQL code to create this table is

create table if not exists

`POI_categories_off (tid int(11) not null,`

`id_domain int(11) not`

`null, visible`

`enum('0','1') default '0',`

`name_1 varchar(250),`

`publicated int(11),`

`publicated_TS`

`datetime, created`

`int(11) not null,`

```
created_TS datetime
not null, modified
int(11),

modified_TS
datetime, deleted
int(11), deleted_TS
datetime, primary
key(tid,id_domain)
)
```

The language field in this table is name_1 where 1 is the id of the language we want to save content for. You have to create a new field entry for every language you want to use.

POI_categories_pub

The MySQL code to create this table is

```
create table if not exists
POI_categories_pub ( tid int(11) not
null,

id_domain int(11) not
null, visible
enum('0','1') default '0',
name_1 varchar(250),

publicated int(11),
publicated_TS
datetime, created
int(11) not null,
created_TS datetime
not null, modified
int(11), modified_TS
datetime, deleted
int(11),
```

```
deleted_TS
datetime, primary
key(tid,id_domain)
)
```

The language field in this table is name_1 where 1 is the id of the language we want to save content for. You have to add a new field entry for every language you want to use.

As you can see POI_categories_off and POI_categories_pub must have the same structure.

POI_points_off

The MySQL code to create this table is create table if not exists POI_points_pub tid int(11) not null,

```
id_domain int(11) not null,
visible enum('0','1') default '0',
id_category int(11),
rating int(11),
lat double,
lng double,
youtube_code varchar(255),
vr_link varchar(255),
web varchar(255),
email varchar(100),
phone varchar(20),
services text,
title_1 varchar(255),
address_1 varchar(255),
description_1 text,
accessibility_1 text,
notes_1 text,
publicated int(11),
publicated_TS datetime,
created int(11) not null,
created_TS datetime not null,
```

```
modified int(11),  
modified_TS datetime,  
deleted int(11),  
deleted_TS datetime, primary key(tid,id_domain)  
)
```

The language fields in this table are title_1, address_1, description_1, accessibility_1 and notes_1 where 1 is the id of the language we want to save content for. You have to add all language fields for every language you want to use.

As you can see POI_points_off and POI_points_pub must have the same structure.